

Working paper – Deliverable 3.4

Hiring discrimination across national contexts

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PATHS2INCLUDE

PATHS 2 INCLUDE

**European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations**

Title: Working paper: Hiring discrimination across national contexts

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Introduction

This Deliverable consists of two studies both deriving from data collected in WP3. Study 1, uses the data from qualitative semi-structured interviews with employers conducted in four countries (Germany, Norway, Poland and Romania) to identify the stages of the recruitment process where hiring discrimination is most likely to occur. Study 2 uses the same qualitative material and combines it with the findings from the factorial survey experiment conducted in the same four countries (see Deliverable D3.1 and Deliverable D3.3 for more details), to probe how (reduced) discrimination bias in hiring relates to companies' efforts to create a more diverse workforce, and how these efforts can be put into practice through appropriate diversity policies and integrative measures at the company level.

Although both Studies are based on the same empirical material, they address the issue of discrimination in hiring from distinct analytical perspectives: On the one hand, Study 1 investigates the significance of soft skills in recruitment processes and their implications for unequal opportunities that fall outside the scope of antidiscrimination laws. On the other hand, study 2 posits that, under conditions of severe labour shortage when companies receive only few job applications their scope for discrimination is diminished. It examines strategies through which work organizations can mitigate such practices at the structural level.

The timing of the PATHS2INCLUDE primary data collection in the second half of 2024 coincided with a phase characterised by both a pronounced shortage of skilled workers and employer-sided high demand for labour and the European Commission presented an action plan to tackle labour and skills shortages in March 2024 (CEDEFOP 2025). Depending on the occupational field, employers were under considerable pressure to find qualified personnel with severely restricted applicant pools. In a such context of reduced demand for jobs, it has been argued that discrimination is a less functional cost-saving strategy when companies hire new personnel (Baert et al. 2015) and that a sufficient supply/reserve of applicants is required for discrimination to occur (Zschirnt & Ruedin, 2016). This is why the PATHS2INCLUDE project focuses on hiring for jobs where competition of job applicants -- and therefore discrimination in hiring -- could still be expected, such as in the occupational field of business and administration associate professionals, information and communications technicians, general and keyboard clerks, numerical and material recording clerks and sales workers, occupational fields which all showed a relatively lower level of labour skills shortage compared to some high-skilled non-manual occupations and skilled manual occupations as well as some elementary occupations (Cedefop 2024, own calculations). Whereas in the former occupations, discrimination in hiring could still be expected, employers should be more inclined to hire a diverse work force in order to be able to fill their positions in the latter occupational fields. As companies often hire across several occupational fields characterised by different levels of labour shortage, the PATHS2INCLUDE interview study has enabled two seemingly contradictory processes to be analysed: discrimination in hiring, as analysed in Study 1, and companies' efforts to hire a more diverse workforce for jobs with a high(er) mismatch between low supply and high demand. In the latter case employers can be expected to take their time to seriously consider candidates, such as migrant workers, who otherwise are quickly rejected in the pre-selection process when there is a surplus of applicants.

Description of data collection in the four countries

A total of 15 semi-structured interviews per country (Germany, Norway, Poland and Romania) were conducted with HR managers, line managers, CEOs and other key personnel decision-makers involved in the recruitment process. The professionals selected for this study had recruited for the following job profiles: ICT technician, office clerk, secretary, bookkeeping clerk, or sales worker. The selection of these occupations was guided by three criteria. First, since the study examined organisational-level determinants of hiring discrimination, the chosen occupations ensured a high level of organisational diversity. The chosen occupations were found across

various industries, regardless of company size or ownership structure which also increased the likelihood that the recruiters to be contacted actually had experience in recruiting for these professions. Second, the study focused on medium-skilled occupations, where discrimination is more likely than in low-skilled jobs (Auer et al., 2018; Hermansen et al., 2024). Finally, only non-licensed occupations were selected to eliminate regulatory influences on candidate evaluations. We aimed at including both male and female employers. Some interviews were conducted in person and some online. All partners used different recruitment methods, but most aimed at contacting employers who have recently hired new employees.

In Germany and Romania, the participants mostly were company owners, HR directors, and managers. Initially, the Romanian research team chose key informants who were either managers or human resources specialists involved in hiring. Initial participants recommended colleagues from other companies. Notably, 14 out of 15 participants were from the private sector. The German research team mainly utilized the "Unternehmen rekrutieren Flüchtlinge" network to identify interviewees. Eleven participants were recruited through this network, three through connections, and one via referral. Of the participants, 14 work in the private sector and one in the public sector. Norwegian participants primarily were line managers but there were also two recruiters working for head hunting companies. The Norwegian team recruited all of the participants through following job advertisements shared on Finn.no -- Norway's largest online marketplace. The team reached out directly to the employers who matched the pre-selected profile using contact details published in the announcements. In Poland, the participants ranged from company owners and directors to HR specialists. Ten worked in private companies, three in public institutions, and two in NGOs. Two participants were headhunters responsible for recruiting for external companies. Most participants were recruited through personal connections and referrals. For more information on how the interview cases relate to industry, sector, company size and locality of the company, the job position as well as the function and gender of the interviewee see Table A1 in appendix.

A common interview guide was jointly developed across the countries and then adjusted to each context. The guide included questions about the recruitment process and how mis-hirings can be avoided, about the institutional requirements that apply to the recruitment process, and the arrival and familiarisation phase of new employees. The major topics were how companies sort out the best candidate and avoid mis-hirings; the typical hiring process; organisational and social job fit; institutional requirements during the hiring process; diversity within the company; onboarding processes; and hiring in general, career development and staff cuts. The interview guide also included questions about company's characteristics, such as the size and composition of the workforce and the interviewee's educational background and current position within the company. All researchers adhered to the ethical requirements and followed the GDPR regulations set in the country where research took place. The whole team used a Norwegian Service for Sensitive Data (TSD), a platform for collecting, storing, analysing and sharing sensitive data in compliance with the Norwegian privacy regulation. All informants received detailed information about the research and purpose of the interview, consent was collected before the start of each interview.

Data collection took place between June 2024 and March 2025. The interviews were transcribed in the language of the interview and then translated into English to enable joint analysis across research teams of different countries. All transcripts were anonymised and pseudonymised. Interviews were analysed following a thematic analysis.

National anti-discrimination policies

Since our research was conducted in Germany, Norway, Poland, and Romania, it is crucial to consider the varying diversity policies in each country. At the European level, the EU equality directives — specifically Council Directives 2000/43/EC, 2000/78/EC, 2002/73/EC, and 2004/113/EC — establish a legal framework that prohibits discrimination on the grounds of race, ethnic origin, religion, age, gender, and other personal characteristics in employment, vocational training, and access to services. While these directives are not migration-specific, they play an important role in shaping the labour market context in which migrants are hired. By ensuring equal treatment and access to employment opportunities, they aim to reduce discriminatory

barriers that often affect migrants, particularly those from racialized or minority backgrounds or those facing multiple forms of disadvantage, such as migrant women.

As these directives act as a framework and minimum standard, EU countries differ in how strictly they formulate national law depending on the cultural context. In all four countries, employers are required to avoid both direct and indirect discrimination in the hiring process. In fact, all countries have regulations prohibiting discrimination on basis of race/ethnicity, gender/sex, sexual orientation, age, religion, belief, and disability. Additionally, there are laws to protect against discrimination in training and workplace conditions. However, all countries have in common that soft skills are not mentioned in their anti-discrimination policies which leaves room for discrimination.

The Working Environment Act (AML) and Equality and Anti-Discrimination Act (LDL) implement the EU directives in Norway. In their larger scope, these directives also protect against workplace discrimination on basis of pregnancy, parental leave in connection with birth or adoption, caregiving responsibilities, gender identity, gender expression, and “other significant personal characteristics” (§1). Having this included, Norway’s laws especially protect the status of women and minority groups. According to § 2, the law applies to all areas of society. Despite the law’s objective of promoting equal treatment, its scope is limited in practice. Employers effectively retain discretion to disregard these provisions when assessing personal suitability and attributes commonly categorized as soft skills (as showcased in study 1).

In Poland, anti-discrimination measures and equal rights for workers are implemented in the Labour Code, particularly in Chapter II a. These measures additionally prohibit discrimination on basis of nationality, political beliefs, union membership, and “employment for a specified or indefinite period or full-time or part-time employment”. Furthermore, employees should be treated equally in terms of establishing and terminating an employment relationship, employment conditions, promotion and access to training to improve professional qualifications, in particular regardless of the above-mentioned grounds.

In Romania, anti-discrimination regulations for employees are laid down in the Romanian Labour Code (Codul Muncii, Law No. 53/2003) and the Administrative Code (Codul administrativ, Emergency Ordinance No. 57/2019). These regulations also protect against discrimination on the grounds of genetic characteristics, national belonging, colour, political opinion, social origin, family situation or responsibility, and membership or trade union activity.

In Germany, the General Equal Treatment Act (AGG) and certain sections of the Social Code (SGB) aim to prevent workplace discrimination of employees. Compared to the other three countries, Germany is far behind: freelancer, volunteers, and interns aren’t in the scope of the employee definition in Germany, which leaves room for discrimination. In addition to that, certain characteristics aren’t included into the German anti-discrimination law like “social status”, “family care responsibilities”, “language”, “chronic illness”, and “gender identity”.

While the equality and anti-discrimination laws in Poland and Romania are embedded in the labour code and thus primarily pertain to the labour market, the laws in Germany and Norway apply to all societal areas and aim to promote formal integration and inclusion. In general, these regulations offer employers a certain degree of discretion, especially in assessing the personal suitability and attributes of applicants. This discretion generates scope for subtle discrimination, particularly against migrant applicants, as unconscious biases or a lack of sensitivity toward cultural differences could influence decision-making.

Study 1: Soft skills and soft spots: Unpacking Structural Opportunities for Discrimination

Introduction

Meritocratic societies are founded on the principle that individuals' positions within the labour market should be determined by their skills and efforts. A fundamental challenge arises, however, when employers fail to fully utilise the skills of the entire population. Such practices undermine the democratic ideals of inclusion and fairness—ideals wherein merit is intended to be the basis of reward—and instead sustain systems in which labour market outcomes are shaped by group-based characteristics rather than individual skills. Notably, numerous social groups continue to experience discrimination, which limits their ability to fully leverage on their skills in comparison to the majority population. Prior research has documented discriminatory practices in the labour market on the basis of ethnicity (De Stasio et al., 2021; Quillian & Midtbøen, 2021), gender (Bielby & Baron, 1986), religion (Koopmans et al., 2019), age (Mulders, 2020), and disability (Bjørnshagen et. al 2025).

The primary focus of this paper is placed on decision-makers - namely, employers - who hold the power to shape labour market outcomes for the individuals seeking employment opportunities. Employers act as gatekeepers to the labour market, making critical decisions concerning recruitment, employment conditions, career progression, and redundancies during downsizing processes (Midtbøen & Rogstad, 2012).

Attractive employment opportunities are limited, which is why research has shown particular interest in how such positions are allocated across different social groups and the systemic consequences this entails. Recruitment, therefore, emerges as a key process to study. It can be conceptualised as comprising multiple phases, each involving a series of minor and major decisions. Four phases are of particular relevance in this paper. The first concerns *job specification* - that is, identifying the organisation's needs and determining how these are communicated to potential applicants. The second phase involves the *preliminary screening* of candidates based on submitted application letters and CVs. The third phase consists of a series of *interviews* with shortlisted candidates, which may also include tests or case assignments intended to provide recruiters with additional insights. The final phase involves making a decision on who should receive the job offer and justifying that choice, often conducted in consultation with the HR department or other advisers in the workplace.

Crucially, the type and quality of information available differs across these stages. In the early screening phase, employers primarily rely on formal qualifications - factors that are easily measurable and thus allow for a relatively direct and arguably objective comparison between candidates. However, discrimination also occurs at this stage, for instance when employers use names as a proxy to distinguish between applicants with domestic and foreign backgrounds. This constitutes a form of discrimination that violates existing regulations.

In the later phases - most notably the job interview stage - selection increasingly relies on more subjective factors. This opens the door to systematic differential treatment, although it does not necessarily amount to a direct breach of anti-discrimination legislation. Several studies have demonstrated that this later stage is particularly critical for the evaluation of so-called "soft skills": not only whether a candidate possesses the necessary technical competencies (hard skills), but also whether they are perceived as a good social fit within the team (soft skills) (Jenkins, 2007; Rivera, 2012; Tholen, 2023).

We ask: *How are soft skills evaluated in the recruitment process, and what consequences does this have for differences in employment opportunities? In what ways do employers' assessments of soft skills shape patterns of discrimination in hiring?*

This question addresses what employers prioritise when selecting candidates. It prompts critical inquiry into how skills are defined, how they are assessed, and which forms of candidate information employers consider credible in decision-making. These considerations also raise broader questions about how employers legitimise their hiring practices.

A key theme here is the importance of context (Midtbøen, 2014). Employers do not act in a vacuum; they are subject to a range of laws and regulations, as well as cultural and economic influences, all of which shape their decision-making processes. Theories explaining discrimination are therefore diverse. One group of studies focuses on individual factors, such as preferences, risk aversion, and psychological mechanisms including implicit and explicit biases. Another group examines contextual variables on—historical, situational, and institutional in nature (Quillian et al., 2019). The approach adopted in this study is contextual and takes as its point of departure the assumption that discrimination does occur. By assuming that employers will discriminate when given the opportunity, the emphasis shifts away from identifying singular causes and towards identifying the stages of the recruitment process where discrimination is most likely to occur. This is consistent with the approach proposed by Petersen & Saporta (2004), who focus on the opportunity structure.

This study is based on qualitative interviews with 60 employers across four countries: Romania, Poland, Germany, and Norway—representing different types of market economies, welfare states models, labour market arrangements and the scope of public policies affecting discrimination. Based on data collected from these four countries, we examine the relationship between hard and soft skills and to explore how opportunity structures contribute to discrimination.

Our contribution is to show that different types of skills are assessed at distinct stages of the recruitment process, and that the existing legal framework is inadequate for addressing discrimination across these stages. Recruitment is often treated legally as a single, discrete event—a ‘black box’—but in reality, it is a multi-stage process in which certain skills may be privileged or penalized at different points. This layered structure allows discrimination to occur subtly yet consequentially, and the resulting ambiguities in the legislation create spaces where such practices can not only occur but also be legitimized. In particular, systematic differential treatment based on social skills is not considered discrimination under current law. Sociologically, however, these disparities represent unjust differential treatment, as “selection on soft skills is tantamount to discrimination against people in vulnerable positions” (e.g., migrants, people with disabilities). The way current regulations operate thus provides employers with the opportunity to justify discrimination under the guise of selecting for soft skills.

Theoretical framework

Opportunity for Discrimination

Recruitment and selection are, by their very nature, forms of differential treatment: one or a few individuals are offered employment, while the majority are not. Given that employment is a scarce resource, the outcomes of recruitment processes necessarily entail inequality. However, inequality in hiring outcomes is not in itself

discriminatory. As Michal Banton (1994:1) points out, differential treatment only constitutes discrimination when it is morally unjust. This perspective underpins, among other things, Norwegian anti-discrimination legislation. In this legal framework, it is not the intent behind an action but its outcome that is decisive: discrimination is defined as unjustifiable differential treatment, with or without intent. Although discrimination always affects individuals, such acts often form part of broader patterns of systemic group-based inequality. Many countries have explicit anti-discrimination laws.

The question, then, is what constitutes "unjustified"? Differences in employment opportunities between individuals are not in themselves indicative of discrimination. Such disparities become discriminatory when they are attributable to ascribed characteristics—such as ethnicity, gender, or age—rather than to job-relevant qualifications. If selection instead reflects actual individual competencies, it is considered legitimate. The qualifications principle — that the most qualified candidate should be hired — is central to fair selection. Consequently, when an employer selects candidate based on group membership rather than relevant job-qualifications, this constitutes discrimination.

At first glance, assessing skills might seem uncontroversial. However, research demonstrates that skills is a complex concept, and that information about skills can also facilitate discriminatory practices. Hard skills — such as formal education and work experience — are relatively easy to measure and can therefore be applied transparently in selection. If Applicant A has better grades or more relevant experience than Applicant B, it appears fair that A is offered the job. This approach is clear, transparent, verifiable, and perceived as legitimate by most. However, in most recruitment processes, assessments of formal skills happen at the initial stage of recruitment, the selection based on CVs and application letters, so theoretically all the candidates that move to subsequent level are formally qualified for the job.

Problems arise when employers also emphasize so-called soft skills — characteristics such as personal style, communication ability, motivation and the capacity to function within a team (Moss & Tilly 1995; Jenkins 2007; Rivera 2012; Tholen 2023). These are difficult to assess objectively. Rivera (2012) refers to this phenomenon as "cultural matching" — that is, employers assess how well a candidate fits in terms of demeanour, behaviour, and style.

Since such evaluations are based on subjective judgment rather than objective criteria, the selection process remains opaque. This opacity complicates efforts to document or challenge decisions that produce systematic disparities in employment opportunities—whether or not these disparities are recognized as discrimination under a legal framework. As Rivera (2012:1001) points out, cultural fit is not merely a preference — it becomes part of the assessment of merit. In this paper we are interested in how this practice persists despite anti-discrimination legislation, and how employers justify placing emphasis on criteria beyond the skills-principle.

One might initially assume that social skills are a universal attribute—varying between individuals, but more or less evenly distributed at the group level. While this may well be the case, it is not the central point in this context. The issue arises when employers hold systematic beliefs about certain types of social skills as constituting the 'ideal employee' *and* these skills (are perceived to) vary between groups.

This phenomenon has previously been documented, whereby employers tend to perceive the 'ideal employee' as someone who demonstrates initiative, but without appearing overly assertive (Rogstad & Sterri, 2018). This reflects a broader concern with being perceived as a socially compatible candidate (Rivera, 2012). Such perceptions represent a form of applicant categorization that may lead to systematic discrimination, particularly when "fitting in" is effectively translated into a requirement that a job applicant aligns with the dominant workplace culture. These mechanisms are in line to what Kanter (1977) refers to as 'homosocial reproduction'

- the tendency to select individuals who resemble oneself. While Kanter originally highlighted gender as a basis for this phenomenon, subsequent research has extended it to include ethnicity (Rivera, 2013; Rogstad & Sterri, 2018) and disability (Østerud, 2023). Recent studies have also demonstrated that employers with elite backgrounds themselves are more likely to favor applicants from similarly privileged social strata (Sølvberg, 2023).

Extensive research on labor market discrimination employs field experiments, controlling for candidates' hard skills as presented on their CV's, and typically focuses in the initial stage of recruitment: who receives a response and is invited to a job interview (see Quillian & Midtbøen, 2021; Lippens, L., Vermeiren, S., & Baert, S. 2021 for overviews). These studies reveal how discrimination occurs in practice, with their strength lying in focusing on actual employer behaviour rather than reported behaviour (Pager & Quillian 2005). This is important because employers may be unwilling to disclose their true motivations or may not fully understand the implications of their actions.

However, since field experiments typically assess discrimination at the first stage - who is invited to an interview - based on CVs and application letters, they generally focus on hard skills. An exception is Ågerström et al. (2012), who incorporate social characteristics in their field experiment to examine the impact of personality as conveyed through the application. Their findings suggest that a warm personality can influence outcomes even at this early stage of recruitment. Nevertheless, field experiments share the limitation of providing only a conservative estimate of discrimination. Receiving an interview invitation does not necessarily indicate genuine consideration; it is relatively low-cost for an employer to invite an additional applicant as a signal of diversity without any real intention of seriously evaluating them (Bjørnseth et al., 2019).

A central critique of such studies is that recruitment is a multi-stage process, with different types of qualifications assessed at different stages. While application letters and CVs primarily convey hard skills, soft skills are typically evaluated during interviews — in the interaction between employer and candidate.

This is not a new insight. Field experiments have served as a starting point for qualitative studies aimed at understanding employer behaviour and decision-making (Midtbøen & Rogstad 2012; Birkelund et al. 2016). A key distinction is often made between individual and contextual explanations for discrimination. Individual explanations include preferences or taste (Becker, 1957), stereotypes (Allport, 1954; Fiske, 1998), and statistical discrimination (Arrow, 1973; Phelps 1972). Contextual explanations focus on institutions, structural conditions, and historical contexts. There is broad agreement that these causal relationships are difficult to isolate (Midtbøen & Rogstad 2012).

One result of the challenge of identifying and studying discrimination directly is the use of the so-called Oaxaca method (1973). Such approach does not examine discrimination directly but rather controls for other plausible explanations of inequality — typically differences in human capital variables. The objective is to isolate an unexplained variance — a residual category not accounted for by legitimate factors, which may therefore be interpreted as discrimination. A critique of this method is that it does not, strictly speaking, examine the core subject of interest — discrimination itself.

An alternative approach is to take discrimination as a premise. Petersen & Saporta (2004) propose not focusing on why discrimination occurs, but rather on where it is most likely to occur. This leads them to emphasize the “context of opportunities” (ibid., 853). Thelen (2009:14) refers to “soft spots” as areas within opportunity structures that exhibit greater flexibility, emerging in the interplay between formal rules, their interpretation, and their enforcement. According to Thelen, this is an important analytical issue, as such nuances are rarely incorporated into analyses of how institutions function. Petersen and Saporta (2004) identify three specific

situations—or “decision nodes” (ibid., 896)—where discrimination is particularly likely to occur: the ease of documentation, the ambiguity of available information, and the accessibility of complaint mechanisms. The first condition suggests that discrimination is more likely when it is difficult or perceived as difficult to gather and document information about candidates. The second, ambiguity of information, highlights that hiring managers vary, and when relevant information is open to interpretation, it becomes difficult to prove a discriminatory decision. The third condition emphasizes the importance of institutional frameworks and legal protections. In short, Petersen & Saporta (ibid, 857) argue that where it is easy to file a discrimination complaint, the likelihood of discrimination is lower than in contexts with less robust legal safeguards. This also relates to the individuals or groups involved: for example, it is easier to discriminate against undocumented immigrants than against those with citizenship and legal protections. When it is difficult to document applicants' qualifications, and when available information is open to subjective interpretation, the risk of discrimination increases. Furthermore, discrimination is less likely where clear rights and enforcement mechanisms exist (*ibid*). In this paper, we argue that the different stages in the recruitment process vary in terms of the reach of the legislation. The porous boundary between soft and hard skills in different selection stages seems to provide an additional context for the employers to choose according to the team fit/the ‘gut feeling’ but justify their choice with the assessable merits.

A central point is that hard and soft skills are assessed differently at different stages. This is an important finding in itself, but it also connects to differences in opportunities for discrimination when considering how these stages relate to existing legislation: anti-discrimination laws primarily regulate the assessment of hard skills. Employers have considerable discretion in evaluating soft skills, relying on subjective judgments. This creates an opportunity structure in which discrimination is more likely to occur. The discretion employers enjoy provides room for action that may lead to discrimination, without the possibility of verification or legal challenge.

Anti-discrimination legislation across four national contexts

There are key similarities and differences between the four countries included in this study—Germany, Norway, Poland, and Romania—regarding their legal frameworks on recruitment and discrimination. The legal framework represents a crucial part of the institutional opportunity structure within which employers make decisions. While employers may act rationally, their freedom to do so is embedded in the surrounding institutional context (Granovetter, 1985). Let us therefore summarize some of the main similarities and differences across the four countries. Despite structural differences, the countries share several core legal features:

Prohibition of Discrimination

All four countries have legislation that prohibits discrimination in employment, particularly in the recruitment phase. These laws address similar protected characteristics, including: Gender, Age, Ethnicity/Race, Religion, Sexual Orientation, and Disability.

Employer Responsibility

Employers in each country have legal obligations to prevent discrimination, although the specific requirements differ:

Germany: Must implement preventive measures, employee training, and accessible complaint procedures (AGG).

Norway: Must actively promote equality and prevent discrimination.

Poland: Must counteract discrimination in recruitment, promotion, and access to training.

Romania: Must ensure equal treatment and access to vocational training opportunities.

Equal Treatment in Recruitment

All four countries legally mandate equal treatment in hiring decisions. Poland and Romania explicitly include promotion and training access in their laws, while Germany and Norway address these through broader principles of equal opportunity and treatment.

However, the countries also diverge in several important respects. These differences can be grouped into three main categories:

Scope and Strength of Legal Frameworks

Germany and Norway have comprehensive anti-discrimination legislation. In contrast, Poland and Romania rely primarily on general provisions in their respective Labour Codes, offering a more limited legal framework. Only Norway extends anti-discrimination protections across all areas of society, whereas the others focus mainly on employment. In Germany, while the AGG applies nationally, enforcement in the public sector varies by region—for example, Berlin has its own anti-discrimination law for public authorities.

- *Protected Grounds and Recognition of Indirect Discrimination*

Norway provides the broadest legal protection, including explicit references to gender identity, gender expression, and caregiving responsibilities. Germany protects a wide range of groups and is moving toward expanding coverage to include social status and gender identity.

Poland includes some additional grounds such as political beliefs and contract type, while Romania follows a more traditional model, focusing on ethnicity, nationality, and skin color.

Importantly, only Germany and Norway clearly define and address indirect discrimination, while this is either not clearly stated or absent in the laws of Poland and Romania.

- *Policy Measures and Contemporary Issues*

Affirmative action and positive special measures are permitted in Germany and Norway, but are not mentioned in Polish or Romanian law. None of the four countries have binding diversity quotas, although the topic is debated in Germany and integrated into equality objectives in parts of Norway's public sector. Germany is the only country that explicitly acknowledges AI-related challenges and algorithmic bias in recruitment. In Poland and Romania, such emerging issues remain unaddressed in the current legal framework.

The Role of Soft Skills

Across all four countries, employers retain considerable discretion in assessing candidates based on soft skills, personal suitability, or cultural fit, as long as these assessments are not explicitly tied to protected characteristics. Norway is the most transparent in acknowledging the tension between anti-discrimination law and employer discretion in evaluating soft skills and personal suitability. Germany provides some legal framing through the AGG, but soft skills remain a blind spot, particularly in cases involving implicit bias or algorithmic decision-making. Poland and Romania do not address soft skills at all in their legal frameworks. These factors

are generally treated as natural aspects of recruitment and are not subject to legal oversight, unless the resulting discrimination is overt and clearly connected to a protected ground.

Data and method

The empirical data for this paper derives from a total of 60 qualitative semi-structured interviews with employers across four countries Germany, Norway, Poland and Romania (15 interviews in each country)¹. We have chosen these four countries specifically because they are interesting to use in a comparative study examining opportunity structure. A certain degree of overlap in institutional structures is important, as it creates a shared foundation for comparison across the countries. At the same time, variation in the opportunity structure was also a deliberate criterion in the country selection process. Such variation is essential for investigating whether differences in institutional conditions influence recruitment practices and the occurrence of discrimination.

The interviews focused on the employers' role as gatekeepers. During the data collection they were asked to guide the researchers through the entire recruitment process and discuss on their decisions. This created space for their reflections on their own choices, how they understand what they do in a broader context of the legal framework and the work team and 'cultural matching' (Rivera, 2012). They were also able to explain and thereby legitimize their reasoning and the information they used when selecting among job-seekers.

Findings

In the presentation of the empirical findings, we will organize the material according to the phases of the recruitment process. While this may appear to be merely descriptive—which it is to some extent—it is also analytically significant. This structure allows us to highlight how the opportunity structure varies across the different phases of recruitment. In the early stages, before employers have met the candidates, they must rely on how the candidates present themselves 'on paper'. In contrast, they gain access to different types of information during the job interview. What is crucial in this context is that "soft spots" are not particularly relevant in the selection of candidates for interview but become more pertinent in the final decision among those who are deemed qualified. It is also worth noting that differential treatment does not necessarily involve choosing an unfit candidate but rather reflects the discrepancy between the selected candidate and the potentially better alternative that was not chosen. The recruitment process could certainly be divided differently, into more or fewer stages, however we arrived at the following division based on the data we collected across the four countries. We first analyse the stage of developing *job-descriptions*, presenting the employers' narratives about the preparations for the following stages in the recruitment process. We then move on to employers discussing the initial *screening of CVs and application letters leading to selection of applicants* before moving on to the descriptions of the job interviews. The last stage we present in this section is the *final selection: a job offer*.

Stage 1: Job-description

Recruitment process starts usually with the companies identifying their hiring needs. The need for recruitment often arises when an employee is leaving and must be replaced, or as a result of the expansion of the company

¹ For a more comprehensive methodological overview see introduction to this deliverable.

and the need for new competencies. When asked, employers typically emphasize that recruiting and finding the right competence is among their most important responsibilities as leaders. At the same time, it is striking how frequently they describe the process as rushed in practice, often resorting to reusing a previous job advertisement and then selecting from a broad pool of applicants (Bjørnset et al., 2019). This is particularly relevant in relation to the role of social skills, as such openness in the recruitment process means that the criteria for which candidates are in fact considered cannot be precisely inferred from the job posting itself.

In some companies, often in the case of the public employers, the opening of a new position needs to be accepted by the appointment committee. Once it is approved, the job posting is drafted in accordance with the needs of the organisation. A job posting includes mainly a job description, remuneration, along with the benefits accompanying working for the employer, required and complementary skills, as well as the description of the company. The required and additional qualifications or experience- traits that are mostly measurable and easy to evaluate.

Well, it is greatly influenced by jurisdiction, especially regarding selection procedures. We are bound by the requirement profile. So, what I write in there must be strictly followed. We often have issues where we specify certain things, and then we receive applications from people who may have a different education background but have excelled in the job. We cannot invite them for an interview, for example, because they do not meet the criteria. So, what we write is quite binding. And the jurisprudence mainly originates from the civil service sector. It's very strong. I'll say it's still, as it exists in almost all public sectors. If one would conduct selection procedures strictly based on evaluation and references, you must opt for what is called the best selection—deciding on the best candidate based on documents and references. (DE_Int11)

As expressed by the employer above, at this stage of the recruitment process the legislation is comprehensible, leaving little room for ambiguities. This is true, especially for employers in the public sector. Most of the employers interviewed in this study discussed this stage as close following of the job description and paying most attention to matching the formal skills required by the position with what is written in the candidates' CVs and motivation letters (at the same time, field experiments show that discrimination occurs already at this stage on the basis of signals of group characteristics in the job applications). Several interviewees did however also refer to the common practice of loosely mentioning personal traits, often described as related to the extrovert types of personalities in the job advertisement. Therefore, already at this stage a preference for certain personal dispositions is expressed in passing. Yet, there is no clear guidance of how this should be followed up by those who handle the selection. One of the recruitment agents from Norway, referred to this by recalling a study analysing job announcements:

The job ad mentions qualifications, and this is what you find in the CV (...) How much have you done this and that? And then there are the personal characteristics described in the ad. Of an analysis of approx. 9,000 ad texts, the term extrovert was mentioned in all the ads. And 'introvert' or terms related to introvert type, were mentioned in seven of the 9,000. How should you make quality assessments before you have interviewed the candidate? (NO_Int1_Recruitment agency)

Therefore, the personal traits mentioned in the job ads are picked up on at later stages of recruitment.

A final point related to job advertisements is that employers often specify that they place emphasis on 'personal suitability' in the actual advertisements for new employees. This is important because it indicates that employers are explicitly acknowledging the significance of social skills in the recruitment process. At the same time, as we shall see, it is striking that there is neither a clear definition of what

makes one candidate more personally suitable than another, nor is it obvious what type of information employers use—or are able to use—to assess a candidate’s competence in this area.

Stage 2: Screening of CVs and application letters leading to selection of applicants

During the first screening, most of the employers’ search for the match between the requirements set out for the new positions with their perception and categorisation of the candidates applying for a job based on what the candidates state in the CVs and motivation letters. Depending on how many candidates send applications, the screening is more or less thorough.

This is the stage where the employers- especially those in the countries with strict anti-discrimination legislation- have quite limited opportunity structure for discriminating. On one hand, they are required to abide by the anti-discrimination legislation and follow the qualification principle, and on the other hand, it is quite easy to expose inaccuracies, especially if the companies are obliged to document the proceedings, as it is more often in the case of public sector employers. There is still some window for employers to follow their personal judgement, also at this phase of the recruitment. Some employers mentioned, for example, that they do not even consider the candidates who send solely CVs or use Artificial Intelligence to write motivation letter. Therefore, already the ‘style’ of the application gives them a hint on the candidate’s personal traits.

It is as awful as it sounds, but if a person today can write a cohesive flow of text it’s already a positive qualification. Lately, young people frequent us with ChatGPT-generated texts. (DE_Int13)

This employer, like others—including some from Norway—points to a challenge that arises when job applicants use AI tools. While the application letters may become more linguistically polished, they also tend to be increasingly similar and thus impersonal. They fail to convey the information recruiters need, to effectively differentiate between candidates. As a result, the overall quality may increase, but the relevance diminishes. This, in turn, can make the social encounter and the applicant’s ability to navigate the job interview even more important than before.

Some employers expressed explicitly that they want to see the sign of commitment from the applicants from the outset of the recruitment process.

So, one thing that is very surprising about this process here, is that there are quite a few, surprisingly many, who have used AI to write applications. Because they are so similar. These applications start in exactly the same way. Yes. I think it’s a bit disqualifying, quite simply. Yes. Especially when you are expected to work with communication, it appears a bit strange. Yes. I think so. And also, because it has the slightly strange results that AI can highlight an experience that we see on our CV that has lasted two months, as a broad experience. Yes. So, it is a bit revealing, quite simply. (NO 14.10)

Although the hard skills are in focus during the first screening, we can see that already at this stage, the ‘soft traits’ of the candidates are being evaluated. Their motivation for getting the job and their showing of commitment is considered in the first selection.

The increasing trends towards labour market flexibility in European countries, including short contracts, agency or on-call contracts means that many- especially young- employees frequently switching jobs (see e.g. Rouvroye et al., 2024). Despite the common understanding that this is today’s reality of many workers, some employers still mentioned that when evaluation the candidates they look at their work record and:

The duration of previous employment is also considered (the longer, the better). (PL_Int08)

Some interviewees placed importance on loyalty, understood as the reasonable expectation that a candidate, if hired, will remain with the organization for a certain period. To assess loyalty, the duration

of previous employment is seen as relevant information. While there may be many reasons why an employee leaves a position, some employers may interpret this as an indicator of stability.

[H]iring a person in the long-term sense. So we want to reduce the turnover rate to save costs, you know, because a recruiting process costs money. That's why the first factor always considered is the topic of loyalty. How loyal or willing to switch is a person? And if you see from the resume that the person changes companies every year somehow, then you have to question how loyal the person is. (DE_Int08)

This is noteworthy partly because it demonstrates that the employers make such (correct or incorrect) inferences from cues in the CVs. It also highlights the wide range of information employers draw on when evaluating whether a candidate is likely to fit within the organization and meet its needs—an assessment that goes beyond hard skills. In Norway—which, as we have seen, has the most comprehensive legislation—not only are there anti-discrimination laws at the individual level, but all public employers and large private companies are also subject to proactive duties to promote diversity. Among the various measures in place is the requirement that employers must invite at least one applicant with a minority background to an interview, provided they meet formal qualifications. The underlying idea is to ensure that minority applicants are not filtered out before advancing to the next stages of the recruitment process. Authorities assume that it is crucial for recruiters and applicants to meet in person, allowing candidates to present dimensions of themselves that may not be evident from their written application materials. However, as mentioned earlier, invitation to the interview bares a relatively low cost for the employers and thus, they can 'follow' the formal regulations of inviting representatives of groups in vulnerable situations without an intent to employ them. As one of the employers (working in the public sector in Norway) explains, she first selects the 'desired candidates' for the interview and then she 'tops up' the list with the candidates she is obliged to invite due to the binding anti-discrimination legislation:

[W]hen we filter out, it is primarily whether [the candidates] meet the target requirements. And then we call in those we feel have the best applications and who come out best. Overall. So then eight or nine people are often called in. And if we have to bring in someone of foreign origin or with reduced functional ability, then they can come on top. So we can quickly have twelve interviews for one position. (NO_Int8)

For this employer, the persons in vulnerable situations do not seem to be considered for selection within the same procedures of as the rest of the prospective employees, but as carry-along applicants. There is no commitment for bringing these 'additional' candidates further in the recruitment process, so the anti-discrimination commitment of the employer stops at the point where they invested their time and effort to conduct interviews with several candidates beyond the ones they genuinely consider. In this case, the legislation is quite inflexible, especially for the public sector, and sets out strict rules regulating the call back. These regulations do not however extend beyond the sole fact of inviting the representatives of groups in vulnerable situations for the interview. Therefore, they leave opportunity for employers to discriminate in the overall process. In Germany the only case when the legislation puts such obligation on the employers to invite job applicants for an interview is when the candidates claim a high disability degree in their written application.

This can be interpreted as an acknowledgment that key elements of the recruitment process occur after candidates have been selected based on formal qualifications. At the same time, existing research has shown that some companies fulfill this obligation by simply inviting one additional minority applicant to an interview. This allows them to report compliance with diversity efforts and formal legal requirements,

while simultaneously indicating that the actual selection takes place in the final phase of the recruitment process.

Stage 3: The job-interview

The job interview is the moment of "clammy hands," where employers and job seekers meet and attempt to understand who the other is—beyond what can be gleaned from the submitted application materials (Rogstad & Sterri, 2018). It is a matter of chemistry, 'gut feelings', and first impressions—a kind of Tinder for working life. At this phase, all (or at least most) of the candidates should have the required skills enlisted in the job advertising, and so the selection takes place between the qualified candidates. It is at this point that the employers start to explicitly refer to soft skills as particularly valuable.

What I focus on is not necessarily specific knowledge, which can be learned quickly these days. I focus on aspects like logical thinking, how they interpret data, how they communicate, and their attitude (...). I pay particular attention to interpersonal skills, not just what is learned. I know this impacts how the person will function in the team later. Having experience with management-related issues, I know that conflicts or misunderstandings can arise within teams, so I also consider how well the person will fit into our structure and how they will interact with others. Basic knowledge is important, but everyone here must have higher education, so nuances like whether someone has read more about our daily work or not, don't determine whether I hire someone or not (...) openness and communication are the top elements I focus on during the interview process. (PL_Int14)

For many of the employers, formal qualifications were referred to as important but not crucial. Most of the employers expressed that the new hires are given opportunities for onboarding, which included both being sent to courses and formal additional training as well as 'learning on the job'.

You bring that person into the company, he has three months in which he has an onboarding period, you have trainings, you have courses where you practice and understand what we do, how we do it, how much we do it, you have an assigned buddy and you have a manager who takes care of you. (RO_Int03)

Therefore, the possible lacks in formal skills among the candidates was not perceived as a great risk among the employers. They were much more preoccupied with the candidate's motivation, personality, communication skills, abilities to learn new thing and fit the team.

Professional suitability is favourable, but I have to specify that we demand little to no prior experience. All training is provided, thus a professional background isn't essential. I'd divide it into 50-50: firstly, personal, interpersonal interaction must be there; individuals skilled in teamwork, be it with peers, superiors, clients, or others. The other half is a fundamental professional work ethic—no demand for commercial training—just a professional approach to work. (...) Consistent, careful, sustained good work is the MOST important (DE_Int13)

You can send people on courses and teach new updates or whatever you need. While personally it is a little more ... It is difficult to go on courses for them anyway. Yes, that's it. (NO_Int14)

This final statement was voiced by many other employers in the study. This also leads us to the next section of this paper, where we reflect more in depth on the essence of this expression.

Fixed (soft) and flexible (hard) skills

A conclusion expressed by the employers, that personality is something fixed and cannot be changed was recurrent across the interviews. It was usually stated in the context of justification of why, at the point of the job interview, they often put more weight on desired personality traits of the candidates than their qualifications.

Competence is important, but it can change, while personality is also important, and it can't change... It's a bit like that.. (NO_Int12)

If previous experience is not necessary or is not that relevant, the most important aspect is the attitude, that is, the desire to learn, openness to feedback and curiosity. Because if there is this attitude and open-mindedness, you can teach anyone anything, if they want to. That is, experience alone is not enough, especially if the attitude is one of "I already know everything, I don't need to learn anything anymore". And when the role did not require a certain experience, the focus was always on the attitude side. And even when experience was required, if we had to decide between several candidates with the same experience, the decision was always towards the candidates with the most open attitude, towards feedback and towards learning. (RO_Int02)

Thus, within the jobs requiring ongoing training and updating knowledge, the employers seem to value openness to learning higher than the knowledge itself. Such commonly repeated statement was often followed by the emphases that most of companies can provide extensive onboarding:

We can teach the job, we have a very good training manual when new staff begin. There is a lot of training, lots of courses, lots of things you do. So if you don't have everything I'm thinking about, you can learn it. But if you are not ... the right personality, then it can be a bigger challenge. Because many people live in their pattern. It will be a bigger challenge for me to change that person, so that it fits in in a way, and that we get the flow and the structure that I want. But the person is more difficult (NO_Int7).

The perception that soft skills are fixed led many employers to seeing the greatest risk of mis-hire in failing on recognising the personal traits of the candidate.

The biggest risks come from adapting to the [organisational] culture (...). I personally see a risk here, because depending on previous experiences and what they were used to, they can adapt more easily or harder to the organizational culture (...). Because there may be people who don't necessarily understand what's going on, don't want to ask or are ashamed to ask or feel like they should already know and don't want to show that they don't know. There is a great openness [within the company] to teach new people who come in, because it is in everyone's interest for the person to be and understand the company as quickly as possible, the processes, what's going on, and to invest time in developing that person. (RO_Int01)

Here again the onboarding plays a crucial role in mitigating the possibility of employing someone with insufficient experience. The employers prefer to take on that risk than to end up employing the person that does not 'fit in' and thus, is less likely to learn from the team:

The greatest risk for me is hiring the wrong person. You can learn a lot from the technical, and you can learn a lot. But we have to have a person who fits in with the team. Those are often the keys to success. (...) What I'm most afraid of is that I will slip-up on personal qualities. And then I'm a little

less afraid of missing out on the professional profile, because one can learn a lot on the job. (NO_Int13)

The suitable 'personal qualities' were most referred to as necessary for the functioning of the team.

Openness is important because we are a group of people who are friendly and approachable. Individuals who come to work solely focused on their tasks and are not pleasant to others would not fit into the group and would likely disrupt the dynamic. Therefore, despite their skills and competencies, we would part ways with such a person. (PL_Int03)

It should always be checked whether there is a person-job fit, i.e., does it fit technically? Is there a person-group fit, does the person fit the social structure? And is there a person-culture, person-organization fit? These are the basic things. Everything is checked based on these three factors; they are all three equally important (DE_Int08)

The organisation- or a team- fit was seen as a crucial clue in the successful recruitment no matter the size of the company or the sector it operates in.

An organisation fit

A mis-hire based on the 'wrong judgement of character' is costly because in most of the jobs the team needs to work well in order to do their job well. As mentioned above, this approach is independent of the size of the company because even the large companies are built of many small departments, groups and teams that work closely together and have their own management structures.

Besides the technical aspect, which is of course important, it is actually more crucial that the person fits into the team, personality-wise. And figuring that out in one or two interviews is quite challenging because one has very, very little time to assess that. (DE_Int04)

Also, some other interviewees referred to this judgement as demanding. On one hand they felt the responsibility of avoiding a mis-hire on the basis of soft skills and on the other hand they were aware that they had limited tools to evaluate them. Selecting candidates based on their soft skills was frequently associated by the employers with following their 'gut feeling' or 'the intuition'. Some of them admitted that sometimes a candidate looks good 'on paper' but after a short interaction they realise that that person is not the right fit for the team. Following the formal expectations against own 'gut feeling' was frequently quoted as the ground for recruitment failure.

After a few recruitment processes, I've learned that sometimes the person who is the best in terms of qualifications may not be the right fit for the team. Even though I had a sense they wouldn't fit, I hired them because they were the most qualified. But after a few recruitments, I've learned to trust my intuition. It's often better to choose someone who is maybe slightly less qualified but fits well and won't be problematic. I've also hired people who did their tasks, but the amount of noise they created around themselves, and the 'scandals' they caused, made it difficult for the whole ministry because everyone had to solve their problems. I felt that type of person could be an issue, but I didn't listen to my intuition, and later it was harder to manage. It wasn't that I couldn't handle it, but it was more difficult. Special management methods had to be applied, such as long listening sessions, for example (PL_Int07).

Some, use an opportunity to introduce the candidates to the team in order to see how they fit.

Technical skills can be further trained. They can be learned. Of course, initially in selection, technical skills are the focus. We often do something not entirely aligned with selection procedures: we let candidates visit the team after the structured interview. They can exchange views, and the team provides feedback, it's just a snapshot, but they give feedback about whether they fit or not. If it doesn't work socially, then parting ways is inevitable. Most times it can be technical reasons, but interpersonal challenges often prevail. (DE_Int11)

According to this employer, there is a higher risk in mis-hire based on the team mis-fit than on the lack of technical competences.

Another employer- that works for a large Norwegian company- mentioned that it is equally important for the job candidates to find out whether they will 'fit in' the job before they start because it is difficult to describe the organisational culture without experiencing it. Therefore, he has introduced a trial day for the persons that receive a job offer, with a guarantee of a job contract from the employer no matter how the days goes.

And then I say that before you can sign the contract, I would like you all to come to a trial day with us. Because I experience too often that someone starts saying that it wasn't quite what I thought. It wasn't quite what I thought. No matter how much I talk about it in an interview, and it starts to annoy me a little, so then we'll have a trial day. But I have to note that they get the job anyway, they, that is. The trial day is made for them. They get to sit with an adviser. They get to see how we measure sales, what the systems are, which customers come, how we sit, how we work, how we communicate. They get to experience a real everyday life. And then there is no, no agenda has been set either. Then they get to experience what the day is like here. I am so confident that the culture here is quite good. So I'm not afraid of anyone saying something wrong, or that they see something in the canteen. (NO_Int15)

The interview stage is the most decisive in the selection of the candidates and yet seems to be least regulated in terms of the evaluation criteria.

Stage 4: Final selection- a job offer

Those employers who provided a brief description of the final selection, often returned to discussing formal qualifications in their justifications for selecting particular candidates. Throughout the study, the employers often mentioned this final phase only in passing as the natural conclusion of the interview stage. However, those of the employers who described it in more detail- alluded to a common conclusion that the candidate with best matching formal competences is offered the job. This is incongruous with the descriptions relating to the previous stage, where the soft skills were described as more important. One of possible explanations for such ambivalence is that, at this stage the anti-discrimination legislation comes again closer to the picture. The employers near the point where they will have to formally explain why they chose one candidate compared to another.

You have to think about how you hire someone, how you recommend someone to be hired. How you justify it for the hiring committee. You justify it mostly with the practical... when you justify it for different actors. You must document all the steps and give evaluation and you justify it mostly with the formal competences and with ... So you can't say it's because of a personality. I mean, you must justify also professional qualifications, why one is better than the other. And one must also write an assessment of personal quality. It is often a bit difficult to write, so we write very vague things there and put most weight on the formal competences. (NO_Int6)

As the employer (working within the public sector) in the above quotation explains, he is required to document the decision making for the hiring committee within his company. Even though there is a space

for making an assessment of personality traits, yet he has to balance the evaluation by putting more emphasis on the formal competences. The strict legislation and high requirement for documentation of the process leaves less space for the 'soft spots' in justification for who is presented with a job contract, however

Discussion

What we observe throughout the four country contexts is that employers follow a particular choreography when selecting candidates, navigating between existing legal frameworks on the one hand, and a self-understanding rooted in moral conduct and meritocratic principles on the other. We argue that the primary form of concealment applied by employers does not consist in covering up their actions or in acting on unconscious biases. On the contrary, their actions are deliberate and intentional. The decisive factor is that as the number of competing candidates decreases, the number of criteria weighed in the decision increases. Hitting the mark—in the sense of appearing as the most suitable candidate—thus becomes a moving target: the rules of the game shift as the process unfolds.

Most of the employers we interviewed are aware of, and explicitly reject, discriminatory practices. One potential limitation of our study is the possibility that we selected informants who are already engaged with, and generally supportive of, diversity. While this may be true, it is nevertheless striking that these same employers adopt practices that can result in systematic differential treatment—not through intent, but through the consequences of their actions.

Specifically, we observe less overt negative discrimination against applicants from minority ethnic backgrounds, and more frequent instances of positive discrimination in favor of candidates perceived as the best "fit" for the workplace. In the final stages of recruitment, social compatibility often becomes the decisive factor, particularly when all remaining candidates are formally qualified.

Who, then, benefits from this form of positive discrimination? Largely, it is those who possess qualities that employers perceive as aligning with the existing work environment. This reflects a process of 'homosocial reproduction' (Kanter 1977), rationalized through references to "social skills," which opens the door to subjective biases. The significance of social skills is especially evident when employers describe mis-hires—not as individuals lacking technical competence, but as those who failed to integrate socially or were seen as lacking motivation or loyalty. These narratives point to implicit ideas about the "ideal worker" and the social traits they are expected to embody.

The pertinent question is: *how do employers understand and legitimise their own practices?* Arguably, this may be the wrong question. Few employers perceive themselves as engaging in discrimination. A more relevant question is: how do they reconcile the differential treatment they enact with the belief that it is not discriminatory?

Crucially, employers do not view such selection criteria as morally indefensible or discriminatory (cf. Banton), which is in line with the legal regulations. On the contrary, selecting the 'best' candidate is seen as a core responsibility in the hiring process. None of the interviewees expressed overtly negative views toward applicants in vulnerable situations. Yet, this differential treatment produces systematic differences in opportunities and thus constitutes a sociological form of discrimination, as the valued attributes often reflect those that employers themselves possess or identify with. By framing social skills as part of merit, these preferences are legitimized as neutral and objective. Although the intention may not be to discriminate, the outcome remains exclusionary.

The explanation lies in the fact that employers operate beyond the scope of legal definitions. This constitutes a 'soft spot' in the institutional framework—an opening through which discrimination can occur. While the law does not explicitly associate soft skills with objective standards, employers often do so in the final stages of recruitment. Differential treatment based on social compatibility is thus seen as both legitimate and meritocratic. However, this is not understood as a departure from formal rules, as most job advertisements already indicate that personal qualities will be considered.

What is critical, firstly, is that the importance of hard skills—initially decisive for selection to the interview stage—is downplayed in the final phase of the recruitment process, while soft skills gain prominence. The underlying logic follows a pattern wherein hard skills are seen as flexible and malleable; a baseline that can be developed through further training to meet the demands of the position. In contrast, soft skills are regarded as fixed—defining attributes perceived as enduring and immutable, effectively constituting a lifetime judgment, a sense of 'as good as it gets'. It is therefore considered reasonable to de-emphasise hard skills in the selection process, as these are traits that can be developed over time. At the same time, placing decisive weight on soft skills is viewed as a form of objective differentiation, as these are believed to reflect stable characteristics inherent to the individual. It is the hard skills that set the framework the job ads, and they are the point of reference when a case of discrimination comes up. However, the actual decision of employment is often based on the job interview when soft skills appear to be the main focus.

In line with the theoretical framework set out for this paper, the opportunity structure for discrimination is shaped differently at different stages of recruitment. Throughout the interviews we were able to observe the shifting narratives on the importance of soft and hard skills. Perhaps the most telling point was that after the description of the value of the soft skills during the interview stage, some employees would quickly switch into explaining that the job offers are provided to the candidates with the most suitable formal competences. *Figure 1* below, portrays our depicting of the selection process within recruitment focusing on the intersection of strength of the legislation and the opportunity structure to discriminate and the weight of the hard and soft skills in the process.

Figure1. Evaluation of formal and soft skills in decision-making during recruitment

In our analyses, we probe this theoretical framework in the context of employers' approach to evaluating soft and hard skills in the recruitment process. We argue that the intersection between the measurable, qualifications and unmeasurable personal traits and the converging values of both during the selection process creates the conditions that enable or facilitate discriminatory practices.

We know from other studies that employers tend to view themselves as open to diversity and as being non-discriminatory in practice (Birkelund et al. 2021). It is therefore important to investigate how they justify their actions. On the one hand, as we demonstrated in the analysis section, some employers describe hard skills as flexible — a foundation for future learning — allowing them to overlook gaps in formal qualifications compared

to other candidates with less desirable personal traits. Soft skills are presented as fixed and immutable, despite the fact that their evaluation is heavily reliant on something as intangible as the ‘gut feeling’. This creates a double standard: employers reserve the right to disregard differences in hard skills while emphasizing soft skills, which cannot be verified and are conditional on subjective interpretation. We argue that this dynamic creates a structural opportunity for discrimination.

Conclusions and recommendations

This study demonstrates the significance of soft skills in recruitment processes and their implications for reproducing structural inequalities that remain beyond the reach of antidiscrimination laws. Employers, in practice, retain wide discretionary power to favour candidates they perceive as more socially compatible, even when these individuals possess lower levels of formal qualifications. Such practices not only legitimize subjective judgments but also reinforce existing hierarchies of class, gender, and ethnicity, thereby perpetuating systemic exclusion within the labour market.

These findings carry important policy implications. Given that it is neither politically desirable nor realistic to eliminate all discretion or the relevance of social skills in hiring processes, alternative measures must be considered. However, the use of discretion should not be equated with allowing discrimination. We therefore argue that the assessment of social skills should be included within the scope of anti-discrimination legislation. The question is how this can occur. We argue, first, that employers must specify which forms of social competence they intend to emphasize and determine the relative weight such competence should carry in comparison to other skills. Moreover, employers could be required to provide clear justifications for the criteria they prioritize in recruitment, so that vague references to “chemistry” or gut feeling during interviews are not deemed sufficient grounds for selection. In doing so, the opportunity structure could be reshaped in a way that better promotes diversity and combats discrimination.

Secondly, it is important to recognise that jobs differ. In some positions—particularly those involving extensive customer interaction—social skills are especially relevant. In others, such as technical roles or positions involving independent work, these skills may be less critical. Under the current opportunity structure, where there is a “soft spot” that allows for discretion and the prioritisation of social skills across all job types, no meaningful distinction is made between different kinds of roles.

We therefore propose that employers should be required to define, prior to the recruitment process, the extent to which social skills are relevant for the specific position in question. If social skills are to be treated as a form of competence on par with work experience or educational qualifications, they should be explicitly assessed—potentially through a points-based system—as part of a comprehensive evaluation of applicants.

Along with policy recommendations, we also argue for a continuous use of qualitative methods to researching discrimination in hiring. Qualitative data are particularly well-suited to capturing complex issues, such as social skills. By allowing informants to express themselves in their own words—what they consider important, what they do, and how they think in practice—researchers can access more nuanced and layered forms of reasoning that better reflect the informants’ actual perspectives than would be possible through standardized response categories predetermined by the researcher. This is especially important when the topic is sensitive, such as discrimination—something most people already recognize as morally wrong and which, in addition, constitutes a violation of anti-discrimination laws in all four countries included in this study. In such cases, it may be more productive to focus on how employers’ reason about concrete situations rather than asking them to reflect abstractly on what they ought to do. The presence of ambivalence is illustrated, for instance, by a German

employer who admitted that his own evaluations “sound awful” yet maintained that assumptions about loyalty and motivation were decisive—and ultimately based on ‘gut feelings’. Our interviews suggest that it is necessary to ask specifically about the quality of social skills, rather than infer their significance based on generalized claims about employee interaction or customer contact. It is important to emphasize, however, that our analytical approach does not equate the use of social skills with discrimination. Rather, our point is that given the existence of discriminatory practices, the final phase of recruitment—where social skills often become decisive.

Study 2: How to Hire Skilled Migrant Workers? Measures for Hiring and Integrating Migrants into Companies

Introduction

Study 2 takes an organisational approach to examining both discrimination (bias) in hiring and companies' efforts to create a more diverse workforce. From this organisational perspective, ethnic discrimination is not primarily a prejudice-based 'individual accident' of human resource managers, but rather a rationalised form of decision-making of companies in the hiring process that is based, beside a cost-saving way to organise the latter, on anticipated 'productive communities' (Leistungsgemeinschaften, a term proposed by Scherr et al. 2015 referring to social fit considerations, with attention to collective productivity) and on considering customer requirements (in the anticipation of customer discrimination as proposed by Becker, 1957). As Imdorf et al. (2025) showed ethnic discrimination in recruitment attempts to protect companies from the risk of anticipated difficulties with new employees. Ethnicity is used as symbolic and organizational resource for trouble avoidance (Imdorf 2017), ensuring perceived service and product quality.

Adopting an organisational approach to ethnic discrimination can overcome the limitations of the two most prominent theories that have dominated research on discriminatory hiring practices to date: the economic concepts of 'statistical discrimination' (Phelps, 1972; Arrow, 1998) and 'tastes for discrimination' (Becker, 1957). The limitation of these concepts lies in the reduction of job applicants to employer's assumptions about their individual productivity (statistical discrimination) or individual preferences (tastes for discrimination), thereby neglecting the organisational need for social cohesion between employees (and employers) in the workplace. Whereas statistical discrimination theory understands discrimination as a result of rational decision-making at the individual level by the recruiter, the organisational approach to discrimination considers the recruiter as organisational member who represents and enforces organisational motives and needs (Imdorf 2017). From this perspective, discrimination can be considered functional for both the reproduction of socially homogeneous work organizations (e.g. with regard to the ethnic identities of co-workers), as well as for a cost-saving execution of the selection process through the use of cost-effective descriptive categories which, in the eyes of recruiters, render an individual assessment of job candidates unnecessary. Cognitive bias and stereotypes which recruiters activate when they 'statistically' discriminate migrant job applicants based on ascriptive categories (e.g. ethnicity, nationality, refugee status) -- whereby the relevant 'statistics' are often only based on experience, if at all -- then also serve the purpose of rational decision-making at the company-level. Indeed, Reskin (2003) has argued that discrimination extends beyond individual psychological and economic factors and includes organisational influences. As social cohesion among company members is essential for a productive workforce, work organisations may discriminate against individuals if they only believe they will disrupt this cohesion. As the organisational anticipation of social cohesion is a matter of past and present experience, positive experience with migrant workers can thereby change recruiters' beliefs and attitudes as has been shown in Norway (Birkelund et al. 2020).

This study's conceptual approach to discrimination therefore departs from the assumption that organisations create environments through organisational policies, resources and measures that enable or prevent discrimination by providing more or less opportunities for the activation of discriminatory prejudices or

stereotypes in organisational decision-making processes. Discrimination is generally defined as the disadvantageous treatment of individuals based on their perceived or assumed group membership. This study does not analyse discriminatory behaviour (and how to prevent it) but is limited to the measuring of discrimination bias, that is the discriminatory perception of migrant job applicants by recruiters in their role as company members with decision-making power. Thereby, we are particularly interested in the dismantling or reduction of "opportunity structure for discrimination" (Petersen & Saporta, 2004) at the company-level through a thoughtful approach to the hiring and integration of migrant job seekers through respective preventative measures implemented by the companies. In the best-case scenario, such preventive measures can be effective to prevent discriminatory behaviour by reducing discrimination bias. The interviews with employers and recruiters conducted within the PATHS2INCLUDE study allowed a focus on organisational strategies that would enable companies to diversify their workforce in the long-run. To put into practice and realize a company's need to diversify its staff in times of skill shortages does not only have consequences for the reorganisation of the recruitment process in the narrower sense, but also, and in particular, for organisational strategies and capacity to better integrate immigrant workers at the company level. The underlying assumption here is that a company that is not prepared for the integration of migrants by implementing inclusive measures following recruitment will not be able to achieve hiring a diverse workforce by simply adapting its recruitment and selection process.

This study integrates both quantitative and qualitative data to better understand how companies avoid hiring discrimination processes by developing and implementing strategies to diversify their human resources development. The quantitative data on the one hand enables to outline discrimination-resilient organisational contexts at the company level. Such contexts can be identified by relating organisational features to more or less pronounced discrimination bias of recruiters who have to assess (hypothetical) applications of skilled migrant job seekers. Qualitative data analysis on the other hand enables to delve deeper into the respective organisational features of companies, that is their structures, mechanisms and policies which foster diversity-oriented hiring processes. In doing so, we try to answer two research questions: What policies/measures enable companies to consider migrants for skilled jobs in Europe in times of labour shortages? How do the respective policies/measures enable companies to implement a heterogenous skilled workforce, with a special focus on migrant job applicants? With these two questions in mind, we first provide a brief overview of anti-discrimination policy at two different levels, national and organisational. We then describe our data collection process as well as the data collected. In the subsequent chapter, we present our findings starting with the quantitative analysis followed by the qualitative analysis, before integrating them in a joint display. Finally, we discuss our findings, their limitations and conclude.

Policy contexts of (non-)discrimination in hiring, with a special focus on organisation-level policies

As outlined above, employers might pre-select candidates based on ascriptive criteria, such as gender, age, or ethnicity, in order to minimize hiring mistakes in times of high demand for jobs, when employers face significant costs from job mismatches. Several policy contexts impact employers' cost calculations and efforts to avoid organisational trouble (Imdorf, 2017). Some policies explicitly aim to reduce discrimination, while others do not claim to do so, but may still impact discriminatory employer behaviour.

At the national level, the employment regime, which encompasses policies and institutional arrangements, plays a crucial role in moderating discriminatory hiring practices by affecting the costs of hiring mistakes and influencing recruitment strategies (Gallie, 2007). Legislation, particularly strong anti-discrimination measures, aims to increase awareness and raise the costs of discriminatory behaviour for employers, potentially reducing

such practices (Larsen & Di Stasio, 2021; see the national laws of Poland, Romania, Norway and Germany summarised in the subchapter 'National anti-discrimination policies' in the introductory chapter of this deliverable, along with the respective analyses in Study 1). Furthermore, these legal frameworks directly and indirectly shape hiring practices, amongst others by regulating the type of information that can be collected about candidates (Quillian et al., 2019). Additionally, migration policy influences the demographic makeup of the labour force. Unfortunately, minority groups may be perceived as a threat, thereby fostering prejudice (Baert, 2018; Quillian et al., 2019; Lippens et al., 2023). Group threat is positively associated with national identification (Verkuyten, 2008) and negatively associated with a lack of support for anti-discrimination policies regarding race (Rosenstein, 2007), minority rights and multiculturalism (Verkuyten, 2008). Although the size of the minority group is not correlated with threat perceptions (Hjerm, 2007; Yaylacı & Bakiner, 2023), people tend to perceive different kinds of threats, such as those relating to safety, money, influence or identity, depending on which minority group they are thinking about (Belán & Popper, 2022).

The contexts of discrimination in hiring are further structured beyond the national context at the industry, occupation and company level. E.g., hiring discrimination is known to be higher in occupations and industries that require a higher level of interaction with customers or other individuals outside the organisation (Imdorf et al., 2025), whereas it is lower in non-profit organisations (Lippens et al., 2023).

Large companies may discriminate less than small and medium-sized enterprises since large companies tend to have more HR professionals and rather apply equality policies (Balsler, 2002; Bruyère et al., 2006). Large organizations often have HR departments that are knowledgeable about anti-discrimination laws and focus on achieving goals like increasing diversity. They are also more visible and face more societal pressure to follow respective norms. In contrast, smaller companies, lacking HR staff, might pay less attention to non-discrimination. Thus, larger organizations are more likely to actively promote diversity to maintain a positive public image and comply with social and legal expectations (see Bjørnshagen, 2022 for an analysis why large employers may discriminate less).

Hence, national policy contexts which reduce or enhance discrimination in hiring need to be distinguished from and complemented with diversity policies at the company level in order to understand the full range of anti-discrimination policies policy-makers can promote to reduce discrimination in hiring. At the company level, diversity can be promoted by encouraging a "cultural opening" and other integrationist approaches (Vassilopoulou et al., 2019). In "Getting to Diversity – what works and what doesn't" Dobbin and Kalev reviewed previous research on which policies failed and which ones worked with a focus on companies based in North America (Dobbin & Kalev, 2022). They state that when it comes to diversity measures, it is important to not treat employees as part of the problem but as part of the solution to embrace diversity in the workplace. With this premise in mind, cultural inclusion trainings for managers have proven (more) effective (Dobbin & Kalev, 2022). While diversity training rather has an opposite effect, cultural inclusion training highlights the goal of better collaboration and communication within the company (Dobbin & Kalev, 2022). This may lead to job advertisements also being distributed on job boards targeted at international and refugee workers and not only on mainstream channels. However, outsourcing the recruitment process may yield the potential to perpetuate bias. The same goes for referral hiring; when a company is already homogenous in regard to ethnicity, (informal) referral hiring usually reinforces a homogenous workforce. In fact, referral hiring is effective when (ethnic) minorities refer their peers, who—once hired—immediately have a buddy at the company. Another strategy to establish a diverse workforce is targeted recruitment which effectively contributes to a higher share of minorities (Dobbin & Kalev, 2022). Beyond recruitment, it is crucial to detect and stop discriminatory practices during the selection process. One way is meticulously assembling and documenting the hiring process (Tosi &

Einbender, 1985; Heilman, 1995; in Petersen & Saporta, 2004). This documentation should be unambiguous so it is more likely that different people interpret it similarly. If people remain being discriminated due to certain characteristics, it is important that they have the necessary resources including the ability to file complainants (Petersen & Saporta, 2004). This will ensure that more cases are brought to court and may lead to setting precedents for future similar proceedings².

Other recent diversity policy research adds to Dobbin and Kalev's (2022) review and highlights a variety of topics. As stated above, legalistic diversity training can lead to less diversity in companies, achieving the opposite of its aim (Dobbin & Kalev, 2022). Onyeador et al. (2021), for example, criticise implicit bias training programmes in companies and suggest alternatives for increasing organisational diversity. These measures range from training staff about bias and the challenges of addressing diversity, to preparing for the behaviour of dominant groups that hinders progress, to advocating for structural interventions to address inequality. This way, feeling resentful or opposing diversity trainings is less likely. Georgeac and Rattan (2023), as well as Brown et al. (2025), focus on employees' sense of belonging. Georgeac and Rattan (2023) found that companies that portray a diverse workforce as a vital resource for increased profits make Black, Indigenous, and People of Colour (BIPOC) employees feel less seen and less included. Brown et al. (2025) and Platania et al. (2025) build on this by emphasising that companies that value diversity and equity make employees feel more motivated to stay and create a greater sense of belonging. Inclusive leadership acts as a mediator between how strongly employees identify with the organisation and their tendency to disengage or engage in addressing an issue within the company (Platania et al. 2025). While Lecours et al. (2025) identify the key competencies that managers need to uphold diversity principles and emphasise the organisational responsibility of fostering these competencies, Gündemir et al. (2024) highlight the resistance to such measures. Additionally, Hachem and Dover (2024) found that implementing diversity initiatives can lead to politically motivated decision-making. This means that, in hiring decisions, liberals tend to act in favour of Black people, while conservatives (mostly white people, and less frequently BIPOC) tend to recommend white people. Bloomaert and Coenders (2024) further analysed the correlation between individual-level factors and support for diversity policies in the workplace. They found that women and ethnic minority members showed more support than men and people from an ethnic majority. Interestingly, disabled people showed higher support for diversity initiatives (Bloomaert & Coenders, 2024). This may be because disabled people are among the most discriminated against groups in the USA (Bezyak et al., 2024) and would benefit most from a more inclusive workplace (Bloomaert & Coenders, 2024). Bezyak et al. (2024) emphasise the importance of training employers and HR professionals in this area to raise awareness of biases against disabled people in the workplace and lead to the development of more effective disability inclusion policies and practices within their organisations. Against this backdrop Study 2 examines what diversity policies enable companies to consider migrants for skilled jobs in Europe in times of labour shortages, and how respective diversity policies enable companies to implement a heterogenous skilled workforce, with a special focus on migrant job applicants.

Data and Methods

A mixed methods approach was applied to triangulate the two research questions and the respective results. As part of a convergent and iterative mixed methods design, an initial quantitative pilot study that included a

² See, for example, the ruling 8 AZR 136/22 of the German Federal Labor Court of June 14, 2023, on the burden of proof in cases of discrimination on the grounds of severe disability.

vignette experiment (factorial survey) was conducted using an online survey of key personnel decision-makers in the recruitment process. Recruiters in four countries – Germany, Norway, Poland, and Romania – were asked, among other things, to evaluate hypothetical job candidates in terms of their hireability for open skilled positions such as ICT technician, secretary, bookkeeping clerk, office clerk, or sales worker. These jobs were chosen because they are not industry-specific, do not face excessive labor shortage, and represent a variety of medium-skilled roles that can be found in all kinds of companies (see 'Description of data collection in the four countries' in the introduction of this deliverable for additional details). Additionally, it was mentioned that the employer received a sufficient number of applications for a open job position. In the respective vignette experiment, participants were tested on to what extent referrals, type of job experience, gender, nationality [native: Ukraine; other country – Syria in DE and NO, Belarus in PL, and Nepal in RO], country of graduation [host vs. home country], level of host country language [C2; B2], partnership status [lives with a partner; lives alone], and parenthood status affected their assessment of the hireability of the hypothetical job candidate. The vignette dimension nationality was used to measure the discrimination bias in the assessment of migrant job applicants from Ukraine or from one of the other countries respectively. The pilot survey questionnaire also included contextual information of the respective assessment, such as recruiter, job, and company characteristics (see Buttler 2024). The latter covered several organisational factors linked to discrimination or inclusive hiring practices, such as recruitment tools (Di Stasio, 2014), recruiters' discretion in decision-making (Petersen & Saporta, 2004), diversity aims (Dobbin & Kalev, 2022), diversity management practices (Dobbin & Kalev, 2022), recruitment panel composition (Petersen & Saporta, 2004), opportunities for professional development (Holzer & Neumark, 2000), and the level of interaction with customers/co-workers (Becker, 1957), that is contextual factors referring to the organisational readiness to hire immigrant workers (Buttler et al. 2025).

Following the pilot survey, an interview guide was developed which took into account some of the concepts already implemented in the survey questionnaire. The semi-structured interviews covered information about the participants and their companies, causes and strategies to avoid hiring mismatches, details about the recruitment process (see Study 1 for an in-depth analysis), selection criteria spanning from organizational-job-fit to personal-job-fit, institutional conditions and organisational opportunity structures, organisational diversity and the organisation of the arrival and establishment phase (see Description of data collection in the four countries in the introductory chapter). In the pilot interviews, the interviewees were also presented with the same vignettes from the quantitative pilot survey. They were asked to indicate whether, based on the information provided, they would decide to invite the hypothetical applicants to an interview and hire them. This feedback was then used to revise the vignettes for the final quantitative survey. Following insights from the pilot interviews, diversity measures in the final survey questionnaire now differentiated between mentoring/buddy programs, support systems for immigrant workers, and opportunities for professional development in general during the induction phase. The final online survey was conducted in November 2024, resulting in a total Sample size of 2087 individuals and 12,522 vignettes (DE: 600 respondents / 3,600 vignettes; NO: 410 respondents / 2,460 vignettes; PL: 586 respondents / 3,516 vignettes; RO: 491 respondents / 2,946 vignettes). For more information on the structure and topics of the questionnaire, see the method report of this survey (Buttler, 2024).

Stepwise multilevel regression models were calculated for the quantitative analysis in order to analyse how organisational factors relate to the recruiter's assessment of job candidates. In the following we only report the predictive margins of the hiring likelihoods (for more detailed information and regression tables see PATHS2INCLUDE Deliverable 3.4: Buttler et al. 2025). The qualitative interviews were analysed using thematic analysis to delve deeper into understanding how companies develop and implement measures to recruit and integrate migrants into skilled jobs. The subsequent integration of the results was carried out using a joint display

to systematically combine the insights from both data collection streams. Figure 1 shows the mixed-method study design.

Figure 1. Visual display of the Mixed-Methods Design³

Findings

Quantitative Results: Organisational Contexts of Discrimination Bias

The quantitative findings from the online factorial survey provide first insights on what diversity policies and measures at the company level are related with less discrimination bias towards migrant job applicants in times of labour shortages. They especially show how specific organisational contexts and features are related to more or less discrimination bias at the level of recruiters. We interpret the quantitative relationship of discrimination bias and organisational contexts in terms of the latter moderating the activation of stereotypes in the assessment of job applicants and thereby triggering more or less discriminatory behaviour of recruiters when making personnel decisions. The size of recruitment panels and promoting professional development are related with less discrimination bias, and so are diversity policy measures at the organisational level (see Buttler et al 2025 for more detailed information). Figure 2 shows how the number of diversity measures in place correlates with the discriminatory bias in the assessment of job seeker’s hiring chances. Whereas, in companies with few diversity policy measures in place, native job candidates are assessed significantly more hireable compared to job candidates from Ukraine and from other migrant groups, the discrimination bias decreases considerably the more diversity policy measures are in place.

³ Figure 1 was created with the help of the AI assistant Napkin AI (<https://www.napkin.ai>).

Figure 2. Hiring likelihood of hypothetical job seekers, by migrant background and the number of diversity policy measures in place

Beyond the number of diversity measures in place, other organisational measures are significantly correlated with recruiters' discrimination bias against job candidates with a migration or refugee background. Besides inclusive hiring practices, the availability of mentoring/buddy programs, support systems for immigrant workers, and opportunities for professional development correlate with less discrimination bias of recruiters. Some other measures seem to matter less to reduce discrimination, e.g., having a diversity task force at the company or offering diversity management training. Figures 3 to 6 provide more detailed information on how specific diversity policy measures matter for the assessment of job candidates with and without migration backgrounds. Figure 3 shows that the significant discrimination bias is considerably reduced if a company has inclusive hiring practices in place. The same applies for having mentoring/buddy programs in place (Figure 4) and for offering organisational support to migrant workers (Figure 5). Especially if no support offers are in place, the ethnic discrimination bias is considerable. Finally, Figure 6 shows how the discrimination bias decreases if companies offer opportunities for professional development for new hires.

Figure 3. Hiring likelihood of hypothetical job seekers, by migrant background and inclusive hiring practices in place

Figure 4. Hiring likelihood of hypothetical job seekers, by migrant background and having mentoring/buddy programs in place

Figure 5. Hiring likelihood of hypothetical job seekers, by migrant background and organisational support measures

Figure 6. Hiring likelihood of hypothetical job seekers, by migrant background and development opportunities offered by the company

Last but not least, some country-specific findings (not shown) hint to stronger effects of diversity policies at the organisational level in the surveyed Polish and German companies compared to those in Norway and Romania. Nevertheless, recruiters in Romania have reported the highest rate of implementation of diversity policies in terms of company demographics. To understand these inconsistent country-specific findings requires further research.

To conclude in a nutshell: Implementing diversity policies may increase the likelihood of hiring job seekers with migrant background even though native job seekers remain favoured, though at a lower degree, in the hiring process in companies that have implemented such measures. Implementing diversity policies and building support programs for new employees can therefore shorten the gap between the hiring likelihood of natives compared to non-native job seekers. Nevertheless, ethnic groups who may be perceived more culturally distant by the recruiters seem to benefit less from these measures than Ukrainian job seekers.

Qualitative Results: Navigating Diversity in Migrant Hiring During Labour Shortages

As previously mentioned, for the qualitative study, 15 interviews were conducted per country (Germany, Norway, Poland, Romania). In Germany and Romania, the interviews predominantly involved company owners, HR directors, and managers. Norwegian interviewees primarily were line managers but also included HR personnel. In Poland, the interviewees were mainly directors, HR personnel, and head-hunters. In the following chapters, for simplicity, we will consistently refer to them as interviewees, even though different positions are included. What unites all the interviewees is their expertise in the recruitment process of their companies. To delve deeper into how companies develop and implement measures to recruit and integrate migrants into skilled jobs, we focused on three central themes from the interview guide.

- a. **The Importance of Proficiency in the Respective Local Language:** The interviews sought to explore the views of interviewees on the relevance of proficiency in the local language for applicants. We were particularly interested in understanding the role that proficiency in the local language plays for interviewees in the recruitment, hiring, and onboarding processes. Additionally, we aimed to understand the reasoning behind these preferences, for example, due to the necessity of frequent customer contact or interactions with public authorities. From the responses of the interviewees, conclusions can be drawn about the potential disadvantages migrant applicants may face and the specific challenges that arise for them as a result.
- b. **Formal (National) and Informal Guidelines:** We explored whether interviewees are required to consider formal national laws and guidelines when recruiting and hiring new employees. Additionally, we inquired about any informal guidelines that the company may have adopted internally.
- c. **Organisational-Level Strategies and Measures:** The interviews investigated how companies design strategies and measures (e.g., onboarding and orientation phases) to successfully integrate new employees, particularly migrants (with refugee backgrounds).

The Importance of Proficiency in the Respective Local Language

When hiring new employees, companies are challenged to identify suitable candidates. In recent years, the category of 'skilled workers' (German: Fachkräfte) has grown in importance in both migration policies and labour market diversity strategies. The definitions differ by country and depend on the economic situation as well as on political circumstances (Boucher, 2019). Therefore, it is important to understand the mechanisms behind skill definitions, diversity policies and hiring practices. Sufficiently high language proficiency in the respective national language can be a decisive prerequisite. This is particularly important for positions with intensive customer contact. In the interviews with interviewees, we asked how important language proficiency is for the position in question. It was particularly interesting to find out why the interviewees consider high language proficiency to be important, and to what extent migrant applicants are also addressed in this context. In the interviews conducted in Germany, Norway, Poland, and Romania, it became clear that proficiency in the respective local language is given substantial importance. In Germany, many of the interviewees mentioned that German is essential in most of the companies surveyed, particularly in administrative departments or in companies with extensive customer interaction. Lack of German proficiency was repeatedly noted as a disqualifier. A German interviewee from the public sector described the situation as follows:

(...) We're increasingly posting positions that actually require German language skills at the C1 level (...) because in the past (...) we've often received applications, even in the engineering field (...) quite frequently (...) from individuals who do not speak German. And therefore, it will increasingly become an entry criterion. In other words, those who do not meet this language level would not make it to the shortlist, because, of course, one could consider offering

additional training, perhaps (...) perhaps one day we might need to be more flexible, but currently, it is indeed a (...) a knockout criterion (...). (DE_Int11, Public sector)

The interviewee explained that German language skills at the C1 level have become an essential requirement for certain positions, particularly due to the rising number of applications from candidates lacking German proficiency, even in fields like engineering. Currently, not meeting this language criterion is a knockout factor, although there is some consideration that additional language training might be necessary in the future. Conversely, in the IT sector, English is commonly used, while in industries like manufacturing and production, proficiency in multiple languages, including English, is generally manageable. One German interviewee described the situation:

We do not work abroad, so German is the number one language and it is also important. Especially on the phone. Communication is important there. In production, it's a bit different, we have people (...) and it's more English there. Depending (...) on where they come from, if they are from Eastern Europe, they either speak English or they have someone to communicate with in Russian, Polish, or otherwise. That is also UNPROBLEMATIC." (DE_Int10, Manufacturing & Production)

According to the interviewee, German is essential for communication, especially by phone. In production, however, English and other languages are manageable due to the diverse linguistic backgrounds of the staff. Additionally, they pointed out in the interview that language proficiency is crucial when assembling products at the customers' place, as it impacts perceived product quality. It can be challenging when a customer cannot understand the person performing the assembly, highlighting the necessity of strong language skills in such. Some interviewees in Germany also pointed out that in the industrial sector (e.g., warehousing and for truck driver), a basic level of German proficiency is necessary to operate machinery and read delivery documents. In Norway, many of the interviewees frequently noted that Norwegian proficiency is crucial for integration and communication, although English is prevalent in certain sectors like IT. A Norwegian interviewee from the ICT sector described the situation:

Much of the language within IT is in English. Many of the terms and technologies are in English. So, then I also usually say that you can take this part here in English. It's going well." (NO_Int02, ICT)

The following interview quote suggests that, although Norwegian is the official working language, there is flexibility in language requirements to accommodate employees who are not yet fluent. The organisation provides time for employees to learn Norwegian, acknowledging that language acquisition can vary from person to person.

We have Norwegian as our working language, but it is not an invariable requirement. We have something English-language in the house, for example, which we do not speak Norwegian, who get some time to learn the language. And for some this is fine, and they learn it quickly. And for others they struggle even longer. But it's going just fine, because we can produce things in English here. And much of what we get in from information from the partner and others, can be done in English anyway. So, it's not a huge language barrier if you know good English." (NO_Int12, Public agency)

While flexibility in language requirements is noted by interviewees in Norway, in Poland, proficiency in Polish was described as essential for positions involving extensive documentation and direct customer interaction. The emphasis on fluent communication skills is articulated as follows:

The communication needs to be fluent, and unfortunately, if someone does not have a very high level of Polish, that is not possible. It's not about a C1 level. It's about language fluency. It's not about the vocabulary or the language itself, but the way of communication. To understand the other side in the communication, in the dialogue. And adjust the way of speaking, speaking pace, or sometimes expression. And also, to respect the person on the other side. And have a lot of knowledge and competencies in disability issues. Because there are many types of disabilities. Now, there are many people, for example, with disorders on the autism spectrum. There is a different approach and different communication there. We are being trained for that. But I haven't found anyone with a non-Polish background who has those competencies." (PL_Int08, Non-Governmental Organisation)

The interviewee explanation suggests that finding qualified individuals with non-Polish backgrounds who meet these requirements is challenging. This highlights the importance of nuanced language skills and specialised training in handling diverse communication needs, which are perceived as lacking in non-native applicants. In contrast, interviewees in Romania pointed out that for international companies, English often takes precedence over the national language. However, local language skills might still be required for certain. A Romanian interviewee from the finance sector described the situation:

(...) in the financial department, there was a role of financial controller a girl who was from Bulgaria and spoke Bulgarian and English. She didn't speak Romanian. She didn't speak fluently. But it wasn't necessary for that role because we, the others she interacted with, spoke English. But if it was necessary for the role, then it wasn't a criterion. I mean, it wasn't just because we wanted her, being in Romania, to speak Romanian. If it wasn't relevant to the role, I wasn't interested." (RO_Int02, Finance)

The interviewee emphasises that language requirements are specific, with English proficiency taking precedence when Romanian is not essential for the job. The focus is on the relevance of the language to the rather than a blanket requirement for Romanian, indicating flexibility and practicality in language expectations based on actual job needs.

The results show that language proficiency requirements vary considerably depending on factors such as job requirements, like intensive customer contact, and industry. In Germany, there is a clear distinction between industrial and administrative tasks. For industrial activities such as warehousing, transportation, and production, basic knowledge of the local language is required to understand safety instructions and delivery documents. However, for tasks involving customer contact, very good proficiency in the local language is essential. In contrast, internationally-oriented companies and sectors such as IT often emphasise English skills, as illustrated by interviews in Norway and Romania. Norwegian interviewees highlighted the use of English in IT, while Romanian interviewees noted that international companies often prefer English over the local language. A Norwegian interviewee pointed out that technology aids, such as AI-generated application materials, were criticised for potentially distorting actual language skills. The interviews reveal that while proficiency in the respective local language is considered important, it is not mandatory for every position. According to the perspectives of the companies as presented by the interviewees, proficiency in English can often suffice, particularly in the IT sector or in internationally oriented companies. As we will see in the chapter after next, the companies surveyed increasingly rely on both internal and external language programs to teach the local language and enhance existing language skills. These efforts help migrant employees integrate into the workplace, opening up opportunities for career growth and adaptability within the company.

The Implementation of Formal (National) and Informal Guidelines

Based on statements from individual interviewees, the examined companies in the four countries exhibit varying approaches to formal and informal guidelines in the recruitment process. The German company cases almost universally report the absence of fixed national guidelines or quotas for personnel recruitment, describing this

as "operational freedom" (Betriebsfreiheit). Nevertheless, some interviewees emphasise the necessity of obtaining residence and work permits for their newly hired staff. Additionally, a few interviewees mention that their companies are too small to be subject to statutory quotas. In the public sector, specific regulations apply, such as the preference for candidates with severe disabilities when equally qualified and the adherence to a 5% quota for persons with disabilities. Moreover, the principle of "selection of the best" is highlighted, where candidates are chosen based on a defined job profile and their qualifications. Some interviewees point to informal practices, such as standardised contracts and hesitations towards applications from direct competitors. While the interviewees frequently discuss diversity and inclusion, set guidelines in this area are often lacking. Interestingly, none of the interviewees in Germany mention or refer to the General Equal Treatment Act (AGG) (see Introduction) when asked about the formal national guidelines that the company must follow in the recruitment process. Instead, questions about informal guidelines reveal an indirect reference, with diversity and inclusion deemed important and attention given to maintaining a diverse workforce (note that most of the examined German companies can be considered interested in hiring refugee workers, given their membership in the network 'Unternehmen integrieren Flüchtlinge', see 'Description of data collection in the four countries' in the introductory chapter). However, the interviewees indicate that there are no documented informal guidelines. Companies that do not actively incorporate the AGG into their formal recruitment processes risk exposing particularly migrant applicants to potential discrimination.

Norwegian company cases highlight the importance of both formal and informal guidelines, as several interviewees emphasise. The interviewees point to the Anti-Discrimination Act (LDL) (see 'National anti-discrimination policies' in the introductory chapter), which governs permissible and impermissible questions in the hiring process and aims to prevent discrimination. According to some interviewees, strict security laws are important in critical industries. In the public sector, formal rules must be strictly followed. Some interviewees explain that diversity goals are supported through initiatives such as those from the Norwegian Directorate of Integration and Diversity, with an expectation that at least 30% of applicants come from ethnically diverse groups. As noted by some interviewees, several companies align themselves with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and integrate diversity into their strategies. The Equality and Anti-Discrimination Act allows differential treatment to be lawful under certain conditions, provided the action is anchored in a legitimate aim, necessary to achieve that aim, and proportionate. The legitimacy of such measures must be substantiated with evidence. However, this regulation offers employers a certain degree of discretion, especially in assessing the personal suitability and attributes of applicants. This discretion can lead to subtle discrimination, particularly against migrant applicants, as unconscious biases or a lack of sensitivity toward cultural differences could influence decision-making.

In the Polish company cases the significance of legal requirements for pay equity and ethical guidelines was pointed out, particularly in the public sector, as noted by some interviewees. Individual interviewees mention that some companies pursue anti-discrimination policies and structured interview processes. The former also emphasised that personal relationships of committee members with candidates must be disclosed to maintain objectivity. In Poland, anti-discrimination regulations are primarily embedded in the Labor Code (see 'National anti-discrimination policies' in the introductory chapter).

Interviewees of the examined Romanian companies indicate that there are no specific quotas or legal mandates for recruiting certain groups, although incentives exist for hiring people with disabilities, as noted by some of them. Compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and external criteria to prevent conflicts of interest was emphasised by three interviewees. Several interviewees mentioned that some companies are developing global diversity and inclusion strategies that promote the rights of LGBT individuals and women in

leadership positions, without implementing formal quotas. The equal treatment of all employees and the prohibition of any form of discrimination are enshrined in the Romanian Labor Code (see 'National anti-discrimination policies' in the introductory chapter). This law governs labour jurisdiction and regulates labour relations, encompassing all actors in the labour market. For migrant applicants, these legal provisions are particularly important as they theoretically offer protection against discrimination and promote equal opportunities in the workplace. However, the infrequent mention of these provisions in the interviews suggests that awareness or active implementation of these regulations might be lacking.

In summary, it appears that interviewees in German and Romanian companies rarely refer to existing anti-discrimination laws when asked about formal national guidelines. In Germany, this question is almost universally denied by interviewees, while in Romania, interviewees more often refer to data protection regulations and disability quotas. Interestingly, German interviewees do indirectly consider the AGG when discussing informal guidelines, highlighting that discrimination based on gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, and race is rejected and part of the company's values—albeit without fixed quotas or documented guidelines. The companies examined in Romania report on global diversity and inclusion strategies that are also not formally documented. The interviewees of the Polish and Norwegian companies refer to existing national anti-discrimination laws, particularly in the public sector. Additionally, there are reports of informal anti-discrimination guidelines in Polish companies and initiative-based diversity goals in Norwegian companies. Regarding the legal frameworks, equality and anti-discrimination laws in Poland and Romania are embedded in the labour code and thus primarily pertain to the labour market. In contrast, these laws in Germany and Norway apply to all societal areas and aim to promote formal integration and inclusion. Although national legal guidelines that should be considered in the recruitment process exist, only a few interviewees in Norway and Poland directly refer to them. The interviewees in the German companies, however, did not address this topic. This suggests that equality and anti-discrimination laws seem not to be particularly salient in the minds of the German and Romanian interviewees. In Norway, there is also a "grey area" in the legal framework that allows for differential treatment under certain conditions, provided it is based on a legitimate aim, is necessary, and remains proportionate. This discretion could offer employers in Norway space for discrimination, particularly against migrant applicants.

In the next section, we analyse organisational-level strategies, policies, and measures that enable companies to implement a heterogeneous skilled workforce, with a special focus on migrant job applicants. At the organisational level, strategies, policies, and measures include various approaches such as onboarding strategies like mentor and buddy systems, training programs that convey company values and communication strategies, as well as language courses.

Organisational-Level Strategies and Measures to Implement Diversity in Hiring

This chapter examines the diverse organisational-level strategies and measures employed by the examined companies in Germany, Norway, Poland, and Romania to successfully integrate new employees, particularly migrants with refugee backgrounds. These organisational strategies vary from flexible, informal methods to more structured procedures. Key components of onboarding strategies include measures for the welcoming and orientation of new hires, such as training programs, mentor and buddy systems for social integration, or targeted measures for the integration of migrants (especially with refugee backgrounds).

The examined German, Polish, and Romanian companies report the absence of formalised onboarding strategies at the company level. Rather, onboarding is conducted flexibly by direct supervisors, line managers, department heads, or colleagues within the department. In contrast some Norwegian companies mention more formal, multi-step onboarding strategies that include technical and soft skill training. Particularly “on-the-job training”

and "learning by doing" are emphasised by Norwegian companies as central to their onboarding strategy. Beyond the development of skills the examined German, Polish, and Romanian companies use buddies or mentors for social integration and the transmission of company values. Formal onboarding processes are mainly found in larger companies. For example, a German company offers a comprehensive support package that includes corporate health management, a works council, an internal advisory service, and mentorship from the HR department. Some German, Polish, and Norwegian companies also report on formats such as expectation-welcome talks, feedback discussions, and conclusion feedback, all designed to support and enhance development and integration. Expectations welcome talks are discussions in which the expectations of both the new employee and the company are recorded, ensuring a structured and efficient induction process. Feedback discussions during the induction period promote communication between the new employee and the company. These conversations give both sides the opportunity to provide feedback and ensure that the integration process runs smoothly. At the end of the probationary period, a final meeting can take place, referred to as 'conclusion feedback'. This meeting reviews whether the expectations of both the employee and the company have been met. These various conversation formats enable the company to improve the onboarding process.

A fundamental aspect of onboarding strategies are training programs, which can occur both internally and externally. These training sessions form part of the onboarding phase and serve to further qualifications, convey company values and communication strategies, and develop the necessary competencies for specific roles. In Germany, one company notes that buddies are required to complete e-learning courses to effectively convey company values. Additionally, there are training sessions for recruiters and managers to raise awareness about demographic shifts and recruiting individuals with refugee backgrounds. Such specific training programs were not explicitly mentioned in the other three countries, although a Romanian interviewee speaks of training tailored to the individual learning needs and styles of employees.

In response to the growing need for skilled labour, three German companies have crafted targeted strategies and measures to attract migrants with refugee backgrounds, streamlining their integration into the workforce. These strategies include offering internal legal consultations and language courses, providing financial support for obtaining driver's licenses, and arranging shared accommodations near the company. All three companies provide comprehensive support for personal matters, which they refer to as "life assistance." In addition, one company helps new employees with refugee background integrate into the community by facilitating their access to local sports clubs, where they can make connections in their new environment. Another company emphasises that collaboration with public authorities and welcome centres is considered extremely important. A German craft company describes how it successfully leveraged the linguistic diversity of its workforce to successfully integrate Ukrainian refugees into the construction industry:

We also have 30 native languages on board, and through this channel, we were able to very quickly (...) in (...) 2022, launch German-Ukrainian language courses because we reached out to all our X hundred employees: A – Who has which native language skills? B – Who wants to get involved in the integration and inclusion of Ukrainian refugees who want to work in construction? (...) We combined the expertise of our skilled workers and foremen with their language skills, Ukrainian and/or Russian, and matched them with Ukrainian colleagues who had an affinity for construction trades. (...) With this approach, we brought the Ukrainians to the colleagues on the construction sites who wanted to contribute." (DE_Int02, Craft Company)

This approach shows that the company can ease the integration of Ukrainian refugees and attract new employees by using targeted language and facilitating skilled workers. Another way in which the company can attract migrant workers, e.g. with a refugee background, is by reducing language barriers to enable them to start work quickly. A German international logistics company describes such a measure as follows:

And now, for example, in the warehousing area, where I'm picking items, I sometimes use the Pick-by-Voice system. This means I wear headphones and I am told in German what I need to take from a particular bin and pack. When I started X years ago, it was like, yes, here people have to know German because they are whispered to in German about what they need. But I said, no, no, no, we have an employee market [candidate-driven market]. That means we have to adapt to the employees. We absolutely have to offer this in different languages now. We're getting there. So, things are developing a bit in that direction." (DE_Int08, International Logistics Company)

The interview quote illustrates that the company perceives a shift in the labour market towards "candidate-driven market" (Arbeitnehmermarkt), which requires adaptations. The Pick-by-Voice system in the warehouse area demonstrates how language barriers are meant to be reduced to enable a faster entry into work. The German company emphasises the necessity of being flexible to the needs of potential employees. The introduction of various language options is a strategic adjustment to enhance the company's attractiveness as an employer and to tap into a new pool of qualified workers.

Two of the three above-mentioned German companies engage in international recruitment and hire employees from non-EU countries. To this end, comprehensive relocation services have been developed, which include legal advisory services, housing search assistance, language courses, and support for private concerns. A key quote from an interviewee at an international logistics company illustrates the scope and resource-intensive nature of these support services:

But organising (...) an apartment, teaching someone who, for example, comes from [Country D] that they have to air out the apartment regularly, how a shutter works, how the key system works here in Germany (...) these are all things WE have to teach the person. They can't just pick it up themselves. And it's a lot of work. Being available 24/7 for the person when there's an emergency like a power outage, which has already happened." (DE_Int08, International Logistics Company)

It is important to note that the three German companies that pursue explicit strategies for recruiting and integrating migrants especially with refugee backgrounds and from non-EU countries are large and, in part, international companies. Recruiting from non-EU countries is a key strategy for acquiring skilled workers, especially among large international companies. The respective examined companies perceive a shift towards a candidate-driven market and develop strategies to gain new access to skilled workers, such as migrants, including those with refugee backgrounds. They prioritise language support, actively reducing language barriers for migrants. This includes measures such as language courses and adapting existing technologies to make them available in multiple languages. While the companies examined in Norway, Poland, and Romania do not cite specific strategies and measures for recruiting and integrating migrants, it should not be overlooked that general company strategies, such as training and buddy programs, can also contribute to the successful integration of migrant workers (note: in the quantitative survey, buddy programs were explicitly queried in terms of diversity measures whereas they were perceived as a general onboarding strategy in some interviews).

Integration of quantitative and qualitative results

In this chapter we integrate the qualitative and quantitative findings to provide a comprehensive understanding of how companies can navigate the challenges of avoiding hiring discrimination and foster a diversity-oriented hiring process. Our quantitative results illustrate which diversity measures seem to be effective to reduce discrimination bias, and thus, in the best-case scenario, discriminatory behaviour. Complementarily, in order to better understand how companies practice inclusive hiring in practice, our qualitative analysis delves into the companies' structures, mechanisms, and policies that underpin diversity-oriented hiring practices. Using this dual-lens approach, we combine and present the quantitative and qualitative results together in a joint display

in Table 1. This table encompasses four categories of diversity policy measures: Inclusive hiring practices, mentoring/buddy programs, organisational support, and development opportunities. The quantitative findings indicate that all four categories have the potential to reduce discrimination biases. From the interviews we learn that national anti-discrimination laws and thus their relevance for inclusive hiring practices were rarely highlighted by German and Romanian companies. Furthermore, in all country cases, informal practises to foster an inclusive workplace seem rarely to be in place. However, mentoring/buddy programs are considered an effective onboarding strategy in the examined German, Romanian and Polish companies while they were not mentioned by the Norwegian interviewees. Implementation ranges from strictly defined to flexible processes. Specific organisational support for migrants was mainly mentioned by four interviewees in German companies and is highly dependent on company resources.

The meta-inferences drawn from the qualitative and quantitative results emphasise that formalised measures to promote diversity and equality can significantly reduce biases in the hiring process. However, there is a risk that migrant applicants may face increased discrimination if national anti-discrimination laws are not adequately considered. Inconsistent informal practices could further exacerbate existing biases as they are heavily influenced by the personal interpretations of those involved in the hiring process. Regardless of company size, mentoring and buddy programs seem to provide effective support by promoting social integration and help to reduce discriminatory biases. The interviews also revealed that targeted support measures for migrants, particularly in higher-skilled professions, are often lacking and depend heavily on a company's resources. Only four interviewees representing German companies mentioned explicit measures for refugees, and these were primarily oriented towards staff in the industrial sector, such as skilled trades. Measures aimed at overcoming language barriers benefit migrants with a refugee background in particular.

The qualitative interviews, conducted with a selected group of companies (see Appendix A1 for details on the interview sample), indicate that measures and policies related to refugee integration were reported primarily by large and often internationally oriented German firms. These include, for example, structured onboarding processes as well as specialized departments addressing demographic change, the development of new recruitment channels (such as recruitment from third countries), or the training of recruiters. Such organizational structures are more likely to be found in companies with greater resources. These findings are in line with previous research showing that primarily larger companies with sufficient resources are able to offer targeted support.

Additionally, opportunities for individual development and training programs help reduce discrimination biases as they promote both professional development and an inclusive corporate culture. Regarding development opportunities, respondents from all four countries reported training programs that are often part of onboarding strategies, aimed at equipping employees for specific tasks and promoting technical skills and soft skills. Quantitative analyses reveal that companies with fewer diversity measures tend to perceive native applicants as more employable, while more measures significantly reduce bias against migrant job applicants. Notably, company-level diversity measures seem to have stronger effects in Poland and Germany than in Norway and Romania. These differences highlight that the impact of diversity policy measures depends not only on their existence but also how they are put into practise at the organisational level. By specifically addressing national and organisational-level policies, companies can optimise the integration of new employees and sustainably reduce discrimination against migrants.

Table 1: Integration of quantitative and qualitative findings on policy measures

Policy Measures	Quantitative results	Qualitative results	Meta-inference
Inclusive hiring practices	When companies implement inclusive hiring practices, the significant discrimination bias is considerably reduced.	National anti-discrimination laws exist in all four countries. The interview findings show that companies in Germany and Romania rarely directly refer to these laws when discussing the formal guidelines, they must adhere to in the recruitment process. In Poland and Norway some companies refer to national anti-discrimination laws, particularly in the public sector. While German and Romanian companies consider diversity and inclusion as important, only the Polish and Norwegian interviewees name specific guidelines or goals.	The quantitative results suggest that formalised and purposefully implemented measures to promote diversity and equality are effective tools in reducing biases in the recruitment process. The qualitative findings indicate that the lack of active integration of national anti-discrimination laws into the recruitment process exposes migrant applicants to potential discrimination. Additionally, inconsistent informal practices can reinforce existing prejudices, as they largely depend on the individual understanding of those involved in the recruitment process.
Mentoring/Buddy programs	When companies have mentoring/buddy programs in place, the significant discrimination bias is considerably reduced.	Onboarding strategies range from flexible, informal methods to more structured procedures, with formal onboarding strategies often found in larger companies. Except for Norway, mentor and buddy systems are highlighted as targeted onboarding strategies in all countries. These systems are designed to promote social integration into the company and convey its values.	Mentoring and buddy programs, according to interview statements, promote social integration and the transmission of values within the company. While larger companies often employ formalised onboarding strategies, buddy systems provide a valuable means to facilitate and support the integration of new employees, regardless of company size. Additionally, quantitative results show that these programs are effective measures for reducing discrimination bias.
Organisational support	When companies provide organisational support for migrants, the significant discrimination bias is considerably reduced. It is also evident that, in the absence of support offers, the ethnic discrimination bias is particularly pronounced.	Targeted organisational support for migrants (with refugee backgrounds) was mentioned in three large German companies. The support includes relocation services, legal advice, housing assistance, language courses, cooperation with authorities and welcome centres, as well as help with personal matters, referred to as "life assistance". In this context, strategies and measures to reduce language barriers are central, such as introducing multilingual communication on construction sites or integrating multilingual options into existing technologies. Notably, migrant workers are primarily employed in industrial sectors such as warehousing, logistics, and skilled trades. In other countries, support offerings are also available, but these are generally aimed at all newly hired employees.	It becomes evident that targeted support measures for migrants (with refugee backgrounds) are rarely observed among the companies from the four countries. Additionally, the implementation of such measures highly depends on the available financial and personnel resources. Notably, these measures are primarily intended for migrant workers in industrial sectors, such as skilled trades, while higher-qualified professions like IT or accounting are not addressed. Nevertheless, migrant applicants (with a refugee background) generally benefit from organisational measures aimed at overcoming language barriers.
Development opportunities	When companies offer professional development opportunities to new employees, the discrimination bias is reduced.	Companies from all four countries report that training programs (external & internal) are part of the onboarding strategies. These programs aim to enhance employees' qualifications, convey company values and communication strategies, and develop the necessary skills for specific tasks. A Romanian company highlights that training programs are tailored to the individual learning needs and styles of employees. A German company reports that there are specialised training sessions for recruiters and managers to raise awareness about diversity and promote the recruitment of migrants (with refugee backgrounds).	Providing development opportunities for new employees is an effective means of reducing discrimination bias. By integrating comprehensive training programs, companies not only establish a foundation for professional growth but also promote an inclusive corporate culture.

Conclusion and Outlook

The main objective of this study is to analyse the organisational policies and measures that help companies to hire migrants for skilled positions during times of labour shortages. The focus is on two central research questions: What policies/measures enable companies to consider migrants for skilled jobs in Europe in times of labour shortages? How do the respective policies/measures enable companies to implement a heterogeneous skilled workforce, with a special focus on migrant job applicants? The conceptual embedding of the research questions takes an organisational approach to examining both discrimination (bias) in hiring and companies' efforts to create a more diverse workforce. From an organisational perspective, ethnic discrimination in hiring is considered a rationalised form of decision-making. Thereby, ethnicity is used as symbolic and organizational resource for trouble avoidance (Imdorf 2017) ensuring perceived service and product quality. The underlying assumption is that organisations, by creating environments through suitable organisational policies, resources and measures, can prevent the activation of their members' discriminatory prejudices or stereotypes in organisational decision-making processes. A mixed method research design is applied to show how organisational contexts matter for the prevention of discrimination in hiring. The quantitative results indicate that companies that prioritise diversity and inclusive practices also exhibit less ethnic discrimination bias when assessing job applications (see Buttler et al. 2025 for a critical reflection on the causality of the two organisational phenomena). To sum up the quantitative findings, the more policy measures a company implements and the more organisational support, development opportunities and buddy/mentoring programs a company has implemented, the more successful the company seems at building a diverse workforce, as the respective policy and support measures correlate with less discrimination bias in the assessment of hypothetical immigrant job applicants. The qualitative findings reveal that, despite a general interest in a diverse workforce, interviewees in all countries assess the local language skills of job applicants, particularly jobs in the public sector, which require higher language proficiency or specific certifications due to occupational safety regulations or customer service requirements. In Norway and Germany, language skills are particularly emphasised, while in Romania, some respondents indicated that proficiency in English is sometimes deemed more important than proficiency in the national language. Although anti-discrimination laws exist in all four countries, they are rarely to never mentioned by interviewees in the examined German and Romanian companies. Some interviewees from Norwegian and Polish companies at least partially reference these laws, particularly in the public sector. The respective laws are intended, among other things, to protect migrants from discrimination and disadvantage during the recruitment process. However, interviews with some HR managers, especially in Germany and Romania, suggest that they are often not aware of these anti-discrimination laws. Rather, it was found that company-level initiatives such as buddy or mentoring programs, as well as internal and external training sessions, are perceived as effective measures, with the exception of interviewees in Norway, who did not mention buddy or mentoring programs. Particularly notable are the findings regarding organisational support for migrants, especially with refugee

backgrounds, however only interviewees in four examined German companies did report such support measures explicitly. The respective companies are larger, partially internationally operating firms that have reflected and addressed demographic changes in their workforce, and who have explored new recruitment opportunities, such as hiring from third countries. However, this recruitment does not target individuals for higher-skilled occupations like IT or accounting but rather for the industrial sector, including storage jobs or trades where labour skills shortage is particularly pronounced and migrant workers, including those with refugee backgrounds, are particularly welcomed.

We can see from both, quantitative and qualitative results, that comprehensive organisational support and inclusive hiring practises can contribute to companies being more likely to hire migrant applicants, including those with a refugee background. However, according to the qualitative interviews, only large companies reported to have such resource-demanding measures in place. This indicates that, in order to enable small and medium-sized companies to implement such measures, for example by designing their job advertisements in multiple languages, by organising language courses, or by offering 'life assistance' with regard to administrative procedures, government support might be helpful for smaller companies to hire more migrant workers, especially those with refugee background. As buddy/mentoring programs can be generally considered an inclusive measure, they can also benefit migrant workers if the buddy speaks the same mother tongue. Once smaller companies have started to diversify their workforce, the resources linked with it, i.e. their different native languages can be used productively and multilingual employees can be targeted as buddies or mentors to onboard new migrant workers. This is a cost-effective measure that companies could implement quickly, and which can also benefit small and medium-sized companies as a kind of team-building measure.

Our study does not come without limitations. On the one hand, the interviews were conducted by different people in different countries. Even though there were shared research objectives, reflected in a common interview schedule, the interviews slightly differed in their style and scope at the level of interviewers and national research teams. Furthermore, the field access in the four countries followed distinct strategies. For instance, the German companies were member of the network Unternehmen integrieren Flüchtlinge (companies integrate refugees) and therefore positively selected regarding their inclusiveness. In other countries, snow-ball sampling was used to reach out to willing companies to participate in the interview study. On the other hand, the data quality of the quantitative online survey differs slightly across and within countries, as the survey institute subcontracted different sub-companies to collect the data.

The different sampling strategies of the company cases in the interview study certainly impact our findings. It is striking that only a few German companies mentioned explicit organisational support measures for migrants in the interviews which is in line with previous research. It is a universal challenge to promote a certain view on (hiring) processes so professionals in crucial positions develop a sense for diversity and intercultural competences (Lecours et al. 2025;

Petzke 2024) and develop inclusive practises at the workplace. At the same time, previous research and our study highlight that companies and migrant applicants benefit from organisational diversity measures. But it is on the public authorities to address and support companies more directly in their endeavour to diversify their workforce, especially at the regional level. Regional governments or councils could promote diversity trainings for HR personnel in companies, offer financial incentives for the instalment of certain diversity measures (e.g. comprehensive organisational support; buddy persons for social integration) and work on the ontology of certain practises/measures. Lessons can also be learned from concepts (strategies & policies) developed and used in the field of international recruitment which could be transferred to diversity policies in general. Providing concepts which are easy to understand and help companies “situate themselves in a self-evident world of diversity, access barriers, and intercultural competence” (Petzke 2024: 91) may help HR personnel to implement a heterogenous skilled workforce and fight discriminatory behaviour within companies.

When it comes to (not) considering national anti-discrimination laws according to the interviewees, it would be presumptuous to assume that companies are blatantly disregarding them, or that they simply aren't considered noteworthy. On the one hand interviewees in some countries (especially in Norway) seem to take anti-discrimination policies more into consideration than in others (especially in Germany). The infrequent mention of these legal provisions – particularly important for migrant applicants as they are supposed to protect against discrimination and promote equal opportunities in the workplace – suggests that awareness or active implementation of these regulations might be lacking in some countries more than in others. On the other hand, we could see that the four German companies which successfully integrated certain diversity measures were able to attract new employees and establish a diverse workforce. As demonstrated by Brown et al. (2025) and Platania et al. (2025), companies and employees alike benefit from diversity measures. Companies can attract and retain employees more effectively, and employees experience a stronger sense of belonging. Therefore, it is worthwhile for companies of all types and sizes to establish and uphold diversity principles. However, it remains an interesting open question whether organisation-level diversity measures are needed to compensate for ineffective national anti-discrimination policies. National policy contexts that reduce or enhance discrimination in hiring must be distinguished from, and complemented by, company-level policies. The interaction between these two levels of anti-discriminatory policies is not yet well understood.

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Appendix 1 Table A1: Overview of Interview Participants and Company Information

ID	Sct	Sz	Ind	Pos	Gnd	Fn	Loc
DE_Int01	Private	34,000	Logistics	office worker & logistics staff	f	HR	metropolitan
DE_Int02	Private	500	Crafts	office Worker & craftworker	f, m	owner & head of marketing	small-town
DE_Int03	Private	20	IT	IT specialist	m, m	owner & IT specialist	small-town
DE_Int04	Private	20	Insurance	office Worker, actuary & IT specialist	m, m	CEO & IT specialist with refugee background	urban
DE_Int05	Private	106	IT	project manager, IT developer & office worker	f	HR, office & marketing management & environmental officer	urban
DE_Int06	Private	38	Retail	retail worker	m, m	owner & store manager	small-town
DE_Int07	Private	30	Tax consultancy	tax consultant & tax assistant	m	tax partner	urban
DE_Int08	Private	34,000	Logistics	office worker & logistics staff	m	head of HR & onboarding logistics operatives	small-town
DE_Int09	Private	12	Tax consultancy	tax consultant & tax assistant	f	owner	urban
DE_Int10	Private	40	Manufacturing & Production	office worker, technician & mechanic	m	owner	rural
DE_Int11	Public	1,300	Public Administration	office worker & administrative worker	f, m	head of HR, internal service & deputy of HR	urban
DE_Int12	Private	139,000	Manufacturing & Production	office worker & sales representative	f	external recruiting & sourcing	metropolitan
DE_Int13	Private	32	Retail	retail worker	m	owner	metropolitan
DE_Int14	Private	131	Sales, Wholesale	apprentice wholesale & warehouse logistics	f	head of HR	small-town
DE_Int15	Private	18	Online Retailer	office worker & sales representative	m	owner	metropolitan
NO_Int01	Private		Recruitment	data & AI specialist	m	HR	metropolitan
NO_Int02	Private	758	ICT	senior data engineer	f	HR	metropolitan
NO_Int03	Private	800	ICT	managing BI consultant	m	line manager	metropolitan
NO_Int04	Private		Recruitment	advisor/accountant	f	HR	metropolitan
NO_Int05	Public	50,000	Public Administration	communication adviser	f	line manager	metropolitan
NO_Int06	Public	430	Public Administration	data scientist	m	line manager	metropolitan
NO_Int07	Public	6,500	Public Administration	office worker	f	line manager	urban
NO_Int08	Public	22,000	Public Administration	consultant (accounting)	f	line manager	metropolitan
NO_Int09	Private	7,600	Accounting	senior adviser (accounting)	f	line manager	metropolitan
NO_Int10	Public	2,700	Transportation	wage consultant (accounting)	f	line manager	small town
NO_Int11	Private	3,000	Communication	sales worker	f	HR	metropolitan
NO_Int12	Public	320	Public Agency	senior consultant	m	line manager	metropolitan
NO_Int13	Private	22	Construction	sales worker	f	line manager	metropolitan
NO_Int14	Private/Public	900	Energy	office worker	f	line manager	metropolitan
NO_Int15	Private	5,000	Insurance	customer consultant	m	HR/line manager	urban

RO_Int01	Private	300 in RO	Food	all positions	f	talent acquisition team leader	urban
RO_Int02	Private	22	Finance	all positions	f	HR director	urban
RO_Int03	Private	2,300 in RO	Beverage	sales worker	m	senior talent acquisition partner	urban
RO_Int04	Private	10 (plus 200 collaborators)	Training & Corporate Services	trainer	m	HR	urban
RO_Int05	Private	485	Metal Manufacturing	factory worker	f	HR	small-town
RO_Int06	Private	870 in RO	Beverage	all positions	f	HR director	urban
RO_Int07	Private	1,200 in RO	Software Development	ICT specialist	f	senior talent acquisition manager	urban
RO_Int08	Private	350-500 in RO	Accounting	secretary, accountant	f	training manager	urban
RO_Int09	Private	over 1,000 in RO	Tire Manufacturing	receptionist	f	recruitment team leader	urban
RO_Int10	Private	1,000 (4,400 in RO)	Entertainment Tech (Gaming)	ITC	f	HR manager & learning & development	urban
RO_Int11	Private	11	Software	ITC	m	partner & technical director	urban
RO_Int12	Private	10	Finance	ITC	f	talent partner	urban
RO_Int13	Private	11	Car Services	workers	m	manager	urban
RO_Int14	Private	300	Events	all positions	m	manager	urban
RO_Int15	Public	4,500	Education	all positions	f	head of HR service	urban
PL_Int01	Public	1,000	Entertainment Tech	all positions, mostly ICT	f	HR & diversity manager	urban
PL_Int02	Private	10,000	Consulting	ICT	m	HR	urban
PL_Int03	Private	13	Accounting	accountants	m	co-owner	urban
PL_Int04	Private	300 (40 in PL)	IT	ICT	m	recruitment	urban
PL_Int05	Private	4,000	Logistics & Automotive	all positions	f	HR business partner	metropolitan
PL_Int06	NGO	150 permanent (100 cooperating)	Social Support	office workers, vocational counsellors	f	HR manager	urban
PL_Int07	Public	270	Public Administration	office workers	m	director	urban
PL_Int08	NGO	11	Social Support	all positions	f	HR	urban
PL_Int09	Private	10	Recruitment	all positions, focus on ICT, finance, analysts, managers	f	headhunter N/A	urban
PL_Int10	Private	40	Recruitment	accounting and finance	m	headhunter N/A	urban
PL_Int11	Private	15k+ worldwide, 1700 in PL	Market Research	all positions in the company, ICT specialists and analysts in the interviewees' team	m	director	urban
PL_Int12	Private	>100	Recruitment	logistics, production specialists, engineers, sales specialists	f	senior recruitment business partner (senior specialist)	urban
PL_Int13	Public	500	Public Administration	office workers	m	mid-level manager	urban
PL_Int14	Public	800	Public Administration	office workers	m	deputy director	urban
PL_Int15	Private	400	Marketing & Telecom	office workers, graphic designers, advertising experts	f	director	urban

Legend: ID = Interview no, **Sct** = Sector (private/public), **Sz** = Firm size (no. of employees), **Ind** = Industry, **Pos** = Position(s) recruited for (e.g. ICT, accountant, office worker), **Gnd** = Gender of informant(s), **Fn** = Function (e.g. HR, line manager), **Loc** = Company location (metropolitan, urban, small-town, rural)

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